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Review of Research Efforts and Approaches to Energy Efficiency Barriers

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ACRONYMS

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
CAPM	Capital Asset Pricing Model
CFL	Compact Fluorescent Lamp
CNG	Compressed Natural Gas
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
ESCoP	Energy Service Provider
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
LBD	Learning By Doing
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MAUT	Multi-Attribute Utility Theory
MAVT	Multi-Attribute Value Theory
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Analysis/Aiding
MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision Making
NAM	Norm Activation Model
NEAT	National Energy Audit Tool
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NPV	Net Present Value
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PC	Personal Computer
R&D	Research and Development
RCT	Randomized Control Trial
ROC	Rank Order Centroid (method)
ROI	Return On Investment
RTC	Rational Theory of Choice
SMART	Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
TRA	Theory of Reasoned Action
WAP	Weatherization Assistance Program
WTA	Willingness To Accept
WTP	Willingness To Pay

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The existence of an energy efficiency gap and market barriers to energy efficiency investment has been known since the early 1970s. Barriers to energy efficiency can be defined as “postulated mechanisms that inhibit investment in technologies that are both energy efficient and economically efficient”.

Based on the theoretical efforts with which energy efficiency barriers are approached, we make a distinction between three major categories of barriers:

- Market failures;
- Behavioural failures;
- Modelling failures.

Within each of those categories, we identify the most relevant types of barriers, describe their main characteristics, and provide a comprehensive overview of empirical research.

The point of departure in all instances are the theories (e.g. Rational Choice Theory or Behavioural economics) that try to explain the existence of those barriers. The boundaries are not always all that clear, as behavioural economics might just as well be called “psychological economics”. Also, “information problems” can be found in all three main categories. In the case of “modelling failures”, the general idea is that there are in fact no barriers, and that market actors always act “rationally”.

There exists limited “hard” empirical evidence for all three categories. The empirical evidence is by no means consistently strong among or across those categories. In fact, even the body of economic research is not conclusive (and to some extent contradictory) on the fundamentals of energy efficiency economics.

Because behavioural economics have thus far avoided the fundamental question of how to reconcile revealed preference theory with the existence of behavioural failures, the last chapter provides a broad overview of multicriteria decision aiding (MCDA) techniques, to find out whether preference elicitation with MCDA may potentially provide part of the answer.

The objective of multicriteria decision aiding (MCDA) is the ex-ante assessment of a few individual alternatives by explicitly considering the subjective preferences of a decision maker for the purpose of decision support.

Brauers and Ginevicius (2009) identify six (6) conditions that a “most robust” MCDA method has to satisfy:

- MCDA has to take into consideration “Consumer Sovereignty”. Consumer sovereignty is the power of consumers to determine what commodities are produced, and suggests that consumers rather than producers are the best judge of what product benefit them the most;
- MCDA has to consider all non-correlated criteria rather than a limited number of criteria;
- MCDA has to consider all interactions between criteria and alternatives at the same time, rather than examining these interactions two by two;
- MCDA has to be non-subjective rather than use subjective estimations;
- MCDA has to be based on cardinal numbers rather than ordinal numbers;
- MCDA has to use the most recent data.

Empirical evidence suggests that MCDA methods are not readily accepted by decision-makers. They tend to prefer relatively simple, easy to understand techniques, which they perceive to be more accurate. The preference elicitation technique (absolute measurement, pairwise comparisons, ordinal judgments, rankings, ...) used within an MCDA method influence the decision-maker’s willingness to accept that MCDA method. For example, compensatory strategies (e.g. pair-wise comparisons between alternatives on some criterion) where the decision-maker has to make explicit trade-off between alternatives may cause “decisional conflict”. Decisional conflict is defined as the negative affective state induced by making trade-off judgments.

Research has not consistently shown that any MCDA method is objectively superior to all other methods.

1. A BIRD'S EYE VIEW ON ENERGY EFFICIENCY BARRIERS

1.1. DEFINITIONS

1.1.1. Energy efficiency gap

The existence of a gap between the potential profitable energy efficiency improvement and the effectively implemented one is clear since the early 1970s (Cagno et al, 2013, p. 291; Cooper, 2013, p. 1). Or according to Gillingham and Palmer (2014), the failure of consumers to make energy saving investments that have positive net present value has been the subject of an economics literature dating back to Hausman (1979) (id. ibid., p. 9).

The term “energy efficiency gap” was first coined by Hirst and Brown (1990).

Some of the definitions of “energy efficiency gap” found in literature are:

- “The energy efficiency gap is the difference between levels of investment in energy efficiency that appear to be cost effective based on engineering-economic analysis and the lower levels actually occurring” (SERI, 1981).
- The energy efficiency gap is defined more broadly to describe the slower than socially optimal rate of diffusion of energy-efficient products (Jaffe & Stavins, 1994).
- “The difference between the actual level of energy efficiency and the higher level that would be cost-effective from the individual's or firm's point of view is often referred to as the ‘efficiency gap’” (IEA, 2007, p. 20).
- The “Energy Efficiency Gap” is the existence of negative-cost energy efficiency investments (Knittel et al, 2015, p. 3).

The terms “energy efficiency gap” and “energy efficiency paradox” are sometimes used interchangeably.

Gillingham and Palmer (2014) see no difference between “energy efficiency gap” and “energy efficiency paradox”, which they describe as the situation where individuals make decisions about energy efficiency that leads to a slower diffusion of energy-efficient products than would be expected if consumers made all positive net present value investments.

Ameli and Brandt (2015) likewise define the “energy efficiency gap” or “energy efficiency paradox” as the phenomenon where “consumers often fail to adopt profitable energy efficiency investments”; or when “there is a difference between the optimal and the actual use of energy efficiency enhancing products”.

However, Gerarden et al (2015) do make an explicit distinction between energy efficiency “gap” and energy efficiency “paradox”:

- The “energy efficiency paradox” is defined as the apparent reality that some energy-efficiency technologies that would pay off for adopters are nevertheless not adopted;
- The “energy-efficiency gap” is defined as the apparent reality that some energy-efficiency technologies that would be „socially efficient” are not adopted (id., ibid., p. 1).

The first definition relates to the issue of private optimality. The second definition relates to the broader concept of social optimality.

1.1.2. Energy efficiency barriers

The “energy efficiency gap” or “energy efficiency paradox” exists due to barriers to energy efficiency..

“The concept of an energy efficiency gap and market barriers to energy efficiency investment has been used since the early 1970s” (Yang, 2013, p. 11).

Sorrell et al, (2000) define barriers to energy efficiency as “*postulated mechanisms that inhibit investment in technologies that are both energy efficient and economically efficient*” (id. Ibid., p. 27).

According to Yang (2013), barriers cause market failures and lead to insufficient investment in energy efficiency (id., ibid., p. 11). However, this refers to the early years of research into the phenomenon of barriers, when the energy efficiency gap was largely attributed to market failures, which occur due to flaws in the way markets work (Chai & Yeo, 2012, p. 461).

1.2. TAXONOMY

Gerarden et al (2015) distinguish between three main categories of energy efficiency barriers:

- Market failures;
- Behavioural effects;
- Modelling flaws.

Based on the categorization of Gerarden et al (2015), and on the theoretical ways in which energy efficiency barriers are approached, we propose the following taxonomy.

Figure 1 Taxonomy of energy efficiency barriers

There exists limited empirical evidence for all three categories, but the empirical evidence is by no means consistently strong among or across these categories (Gerarden et al, 2015). In fact, even “... the body of economic research is not conclusive (and to some extent contradictory) on the basics of energy efficiency economics” (Knittel et al, 2015, p. 6).

1.3. A SIMPLE FRAMEWORK TO UNDERSTAND ENERGY EFFICIENCY BARRIERS

“There is a large body of literature on the nature of barriers to energy efficiency at the micro and the macro level, which draws on partly overlapping concepts from neo-classical economics, institutional

economics (including principal-agent theory and transaction cost economics), behavioural economics, psychology and sociology” (Schleich & Gruber, 2008, p 1-2).

In standard neoclassic economic theory rational consumers allocate their resources to the commodities (goods, services) that minimize their present total cost of ownership.

Knittel (2014) presents a simple analytical framework that mirrors the behaviour of a rational consumer under the neoclassical economics perspective; and that captures the basic economics of an investment in an energy efficiency technology.

The utility-maximizing consumer has to choose between an energy-efficient and a standard technology. The decision-maker has to weigh the future uncertain energy savings against the extra cost of the investment in the energy-efficiency technology. The decision will depend on market conditions, the existence of potential “market failures”, and potentially so-called consumer non-rational behaviour (“behavioural failures”).

The consumer will decide to buy the energy efficient technology if he expects the present-discounted value of all future savings plus (or minus) any potential non-observable gains (or losses) to exceed the net present value (NPV) of the payments towards covering the extra cost of the energy-efficiency technology.

Three additional considerations complicate this simple decision rule:

- potential aspects of the market that might reduce the amount of energy savings captured by the decision-maker (see also the chapter on “market failures”);
- effects that may lead consumers to undervalue the energy savings from investing in an energy efficient technology (see also the chapter on “behavioural failures”);
- potential option value from delaying an investment in an energy efficient technology (see also the chapter on “modelling flaws”).

This simple intuitive energy-efficiency economic model can be written as

$$\gamma NPV_{savings} + \varphi \geq NPV_{\Delta investment} + Option\ value\ of\ waiting$$

where

- $NPV_{savings}$ is the present discounted value of the expected future savings in energy costs from the energy-efficiency investment;
- γ is the term meant to capture the behavioural failures, i.e. the effects that might lead consumers to undervalue the energy savings from investing in energy efficiency;
- φ is the term meant to capture the market failures, that might reduce the amount of energy costs savings;
- $NPV_{\Delta investment}$ is the present discounted value of the difference between the investment costs of the energy-efficiency technology and the standard technology;
- *Option value of waiting* captures any potential option value from delaying the investment in energy efficiency.

The γ and φ terms and their components will be explained in greater detail in the following chapters, as well as the “option value of waiting” and other “modelling failures”.

Knittel et al. conclude their paper with the phrase: “*Solving the energy efficiency gap begins with solving the energy efficiency **research** gap.*” This report aims to give a comprehensive overview of the research so far.

2. MARKET FAILURES

2.1. INTRODUCTION TO MARKET FAILURES

Barriers to energy efficiency were initially explained using theories from mainstream economics (Chai & Yeo, 2012, p. 461). Neoclassical economics assumes that consumers and producers have perfect information and act in a strictly rational fashion leading markets to be efficient (Cooper, 2013, p. 4).

Engineers, economists and policy analysts have long recognized that “market failures” (including lack of information, principal-agent problems and inefficient pricing of energy) can lead to inefficiently low levels of investment in energy efficiency (Gillingham, Newell & Palmer, 2009, p. 19). For instance, Koomey and Sanstad (1994) state that “market failures” may exist that keep consumers and firms from investing in energy efficiency even when the lifetime savings exceed the lifetime costs of the investment.

The conventional standard framework for dealing with energy efficiency barriers is thus based on the analysis of market failures (Ramos et al, 2015, p. 1).

Market failures occur when there is a flaw in the way markets operate. They are conditions of a market that violate one or more of the neoclassical economic assumptions that define an ideal market for products or services such as rational behaviour and perfect information.

Market failures include:

- Information problems (e.g. imperfect information and principal-agent issues);
- Energy market failures (e.g. unpriced externalities and average-cost electricity pricing);
- Capital market failures (e.g. liquidity constraints);
- Innovation market failures (e.g. information spillover from R&D).

2.2. INFORMATION PROBLEMS

According to neoclassical economics, agents maximize expected utility using exponential discounting, and they have access to information that they can assess freely and completely (Pollit et al, 2011). “The efficient working of the market depends on the parties to transactions having adequate information” (Cagno et al, 2013, p. 291).

The most relevant information problems are:

- Imperfect information (lack of information on the part of the consumers, including underprovision due to public good aspects);
- Split Incentives (such as the „landlord-tenant“ problem);
- Asymmetric information (adverse selection, moral hazard);
- Learning-by-using spillovers.

Principal agent problems such as split incentives and asymmetric information indisputably belong to the so-called market failures. The situation is not so clear for “imperfect information”, because some of those information problems belong to the category of behavioural failures, whereas others could or should be categorized under modelling failures. More in particular, it is not very clear whether the “lack of information” problem as a result of “transaction costs” (as acquiring and processing information may be costly) should be categorized as a “market failure”; or as a “modelling failure” (as transaction costs may be considered so-called unobserved). We refer to the chapter on modelling failures.

2.2.1. Imperfect information

2.2.1.1. Problem definition

Consumers are often poorly informed about market conditions, technology characteristics and their own energy use.

Markets for energy services are susceptible to information failures.

Markets may supply imperfect information about energy-efficiency technologies, because the manufacturers and early adopters who generate the information may realize little private return. The information is social: it simultaneously benefits an unlimited number of individuals and anyone can freely disseminate it (Austin, 2012, p. 9-10).

The markets may thus not deliver enough quality information about the energy performance and opportunities of different technologies, leading to cost-effective decisions being missed and sub-investment in energy efficiency.

This has been observed in literature many times.

- The lack of information may lead to cost-effective energy efficiency measures opportunities being missed (Howarth & Andersson, 1993);
- The lack of adequate information about potential energy-efficient technologies inhibits investments in energy efficiency measures (Sanstad and Howarth, 1994);
- "... insufficient information about the energy performance of different technologies lead consumers to make sub-optimal decisions based on provisional and uncertain information" (Cagno et al, 2013, p. 292);
- Decision-makers may not have all of the information available to them to correctly value the investment alternatives, which requires knowledge of energy prices, and the relative energy use of the standard and energy-efficient technologies both in the current period and in the future. (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 12).

Types of imperfect information are (Ameli & Brandt, 2015):

- The lack of access to information, i.e. insufficient information because for instance the energy performance of energy efficient technologies is not made available to agents;
- The accuracy of the available information, i.e. the information provider may not always be transparent about the product being offered.

End users do not observe the amount of energy consumed by energy efficient technologies such as heating and cooling systems, lighting systems and appliances, making energy efficiency an intangible characteristic of those technologies. The "lack of information" barrier also includes the lack of knowledge about energy costs, even though they may represent a significant part of household income (Ramos et al, 2015).

The imperfect information barrier is likely to be more of a problem when (Cagno et al, 2013):

- the product is purchased infrequently (for example large investments in new and more energy efficient technologies);
- the rate of technology change is rapid relative to the interval between purchases;
- it is difficult to quantify the energy savings that resulted from the installation of an energy-efficiency technology, as usage patterns may have changed.

2.2.1.2. Empirical evidence for the "lack of information" barrier

There are plenty of examples of the "lack of information" barrier in literature.

Few consumers know the costs and benefits of energy-efficiency technologies; how much energy they consume or what rates of return to expect from energy-efficiency measures (Hawker et al, 1999).

Few of the 57 households in a survey understood the financial calculations behind the payback of investments. Those who did, did not apply that knowledge to their vehicle purchase and use (Turrentine & Kurani, 2007).

Households in the national U.S. Survey apparently have limited knowledge regarding the effectiveness of energy-efficiency measures. The participants mention curtailment rather than energy-efficiency improvements as more effective (Atari et al, 2010).

Most respondents in several experiments tend to believe that the amount of gasoline / petrol consumed by a car decreases as a linear function of a car's mile per gallon (MPG). In reality it follows a curvilinear – similar to hyperbolic – function (Larrick & Sol, 2008). This is also known as the “MPG illusion”.

A survey by Jessoe and Rapson of residential bill-payers in Connecticut in 2010 revealed that only 51% of households correctly identified whether they paid flat or time-of-use (TOU) rates; and only 44% (64%) correctly identified their previous month's billed amount within 20% (50%) of the actual amount (Rapson, 2013).

Consumers misperceive the fuel economy of cars, either by underestimating the financial savings or by being subject to the MPG illusion (based on data of the Vehicle Ownership Alternatives Survey). Some consumers incorrectly categorised similar vehicles as having the same MPG; others correctly assessed the MPG difference but overstated the importance of the difference (Allcott, 2013).

Around 50% of the respondents of a survey of 1,721 households in the Netherlands did not know their energy expenses (on average 222 EUR or 8% of income) (Brounen et al, 2013).

In an OECD Survey on Environmental Behaviour & Attitudes, on average across countries only 55% of households were able to provide information about their energy spending; and only 19% on energy use in volumes. Those who were able to provide information about their energy bill were more likely to invest in light bulbs; those who were able to provide information about number of kilowatt hours used were more likely to invest in energy-efficiency appliances (Ameli & Brandt, 2014).

2.2.1.3. Empirical evidence based on the assessment of EPCs

It is difficult to measure how “imperfect information” affects energy-efficiency investments in a market as complex as energy-efficiency in buildings. Ramos et al. (2015) review empirical evidence on the performance of information-based policy instruments.

There is empirical research that assesses the impact of energy performance certificates (EPCs) on the end-users' decision-making and the market price of buildings. This research uses methods (econometric models) that determine the willingness-to-pay (WTP) of buyers or renters based on certain (hedonistic) characteristics such as vintage, location, thermal insulation of the building, etc. The data are derived from real estate transaction databases and other databases. The results are summarized by Ramos et al. (2015, p. 10).

Table 1 Assessment of the effect of energy performance certificates (EPC) for buildings

Study	Sector	Willingness-to-pay WTP	
		Rent (effective)	Sales
Eichholtz et al (2010)	Commercial U.S.	3% (7%)	16%
Eichholts et al (2013)	Commercial U.S.	3% (8%)	13%
Wiley et al (2010)	Commercial U.S.	7-9% Energy Star 15-17% LEED	30\$/f ² Energy Star 130\$/Fé leed
Fuerst & McAllister (2011a)	Commercial U.S.	4-5%	25%
Fuerst & McAllister (2011c)	Commercial U.S.	3% Energy Star 5% LEED 9% Energy Star + LEED	18% Energy Star 25% LEED 28-29% Energy Star + LEED
Reichardt et al (2012)	Commercial U.S.	2.5% Energy Star 2.9% LEED	
Das et al (2011)	Commercial U.S.	Positive and dynamic	
Bloom et al (2011)	Commercial U.S.		8.66\$/f ²
Kok & Jennen (2012)	Commercial Netherlands	-6%	
Fuerst & McAllister (2011b)	Commercial UK	Not significant	Not significant
Chegut et al (2013)	Commercial London	19.7%	14.7%
Brounen & Kok (2011)	Residential Netherlands		3.6%
Högberg (2013)	Residential Sweden		Positive WTP

Hyland et al (2013)	Residential Ireland	A: 1.8% B: 3.9% C: not significant E: -1.9% F/G: -3.2%	A: 9.3% B: 5.2% C: 1.7% E: not significant F/G: -10.6%
Cajias & Piazzolo (2013)	Residential Germany	Total returns: B: 2.27% C: 2.34% D: 2.69% E/F: not significant G: reference	
Yoshida & Sugiura (2011)	Residential Tokyo		Negative
Deng et al (2012)	Residential Singapore		4%
Zheng et al (2012)	Residential Beijing	Negative	Negative
Wall et al (2013)	Residential U.S.		Positive houses 1996-2005 Not significant newer houses Values reach up to 20%
Kahn & Kok (2014)	Residential California		9%

Source: Ramos et al. (2015)

The results for the residential sector in EU overwhelmingly point to a positive WTP for certified dwellings. Chegut et al (2013) found a positive effect for the commercial sector in London; and Kok and Jennen (2012) for the commercial sector in the Netherlands. Fuerst and McAllister (2011) did not find any effect for the commercial sector in the UK.

Ramos et al (2015) also summarize estimations of WTP from stated preferences for appliances.

Table 2 Assessment of the effect of energy performance certificates (EPC) for appliances

Study	Sector	Willingness-to-pay WTP
Galarraga et al (2011)	Dishwashers Spain	15.6%
Sammer & Wüstnehaugen (2006)	Washing machines Switzerland	Positive
Wallander (2008)	Washing machines U.S.	Not significant
Shan & Saijo (2009)	Refrigerators and air-conditioners Shanghai	Positive with large variation
Ward et al (2011)	Refrigerators U.S.	Positive
Newell & Siikamäki (2014)	Water heaters U.S.	Depends on the disclosed information
Houde (2014a)	Refrigerators U.S.	Positive for some groups

Source: Ramos et al. (2015).

Galarraga et al (2011) use hedonic pricing to estimate the WTP for efficient dishwashers in Spain; Sammer and Wüstenhagen (2006) for washing machines in Switzerland.

Table 3 Assessment of the effect of energy performance certificates (EPC) for private cars

Study	Sector	Willingness-to-pay WTP
Galarraga et al (2014)	Private cars Spain	Positive
Alberini et al (2014)	Private cars Switzerland	Positive

Source: Ramos et al. (2015).

Galarraga et al. (2014) find that in Spain efficient cars (with an A or B certificate) are sold at a premium between 2.1% and 9%. Alberini et al. (2014) show that in Switzerland the price of an A label vehicle ranges between 5% and 6 to 11%,

2.2.2. Principal Agent (PA) Problems

Principal-agent problems may arise when intermediaries are involved in the decisions to invest in energy-saving technologies; or when the persons responsible for the investment decisions are different from those benefiting from the energy savings (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

In the literature on energy efficiency barriers the Principal-Agent problem usually refers to the phenomenon where the economic agent making an energy efficiency investment (the Agent) is not the same as the one that will profit from the investment (the Principal). Economic theory explains how in these situations the investment in the energy efficiency technologies may be less than the social optimal (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 13).

There are a number of relationships that suffer from the Principal-Agent market failure.

Knittel et al, (2014) provide the following examples:

- The relation between the energy utility and the energy customer. The electric utility has no incentive to promote energy efficiency among its consumers, when they charge consumers volumetric tariffs (in €/MWh). Promoting energy efficiency would lower the revenues collected by the utility from consumers;
- The relation between the landlord and the tenant. Tenants (Principal) pay for the monthly electricity bills and they pay more or less depending on the products bought by the landlord (Agent). The landlord does not have sufficient incentive to invest in energy efficient products, unless the value of the energy efficiency investments are completely capitalized into rents.

Giraudet et al. (2012) describe the Principal-Agent problem as the relationship where an agent has the authority to act on behalf of a consumer (the principal), but does not fully reflect the consumer's best interests. They provide a number of examples:

- Architects, engineers, and builders (Agent), who generally seek to minimize first costs, select the energy technologies that homeowners and apartment dwellers (Principal) must use. In this particular case, the consumer's best interest would be better met by selecting technologies based on life-cycle costs;
- Industrial buyers (Agent) choose the technologies that are used in the production process and are mainly concerned with availability and the known dependability of standard equipment;
- Principal-agent relationship may arise due to a lack of trust between two parties at different levels within an organization or transaction. The owner of a company (Principal), who may not be as well-informed about the site-specific criteria for energy efficiency investments, may demand short payback rates or high hurdle rates on energy efficiency investments due to his or her distrust in the executive's (Agent) ability to convey such investments—leading to the neglect of cost-effective energy efficiency investments (DeCanio, 1993; Jaffe and Stavins, 1994). Strict monitoring and control by the principal, since he cannot observe what the agent is doing, may result in the overlooking of energy efficiency measures (Jaffe and Stavins, 1994).

In principle, one should make a clear distinction between split incentives and asymmetric information (Andersen & Bleischwitz, 2009, p. 2):

- Split incentives. The „split incentives between principals and agents“ barrier deviates from traditional Principal-Agent problems, because the problem is caused by a split between the investor and the user of technologies, and not by asymmetries of information;
- Asymmetric information. The market barriers arising through informational asymmetries are inefficiencies caused by the problem of „adverse selection“ and „moral hazard“.

Figure 2 Principal-Agent (PA) problems

The focus in the literature on agency barriers has largely been on the problem of “split incentives” There seem to be a lack of theoretical descriptions on how informational asymmetries impact the outcome of energy efficiency (Andersen & Bleischwitz, 2009, p. 2).

2.2.2.1. Split Incentives

Split incentives refers to the situation where the actors who make the decision about which technologies to use (Agent) are not responsible for paying the energy bills (Principal).

If a person cannot benefit from an energy efficiency investment, the most likely outcome is the non-take-up of the measure (Hirst and Brown, 1990; Jaffe and Stavins, 1994).

One of the most frequently cited examples is the “landlord-tenant” relationship. The landlord-tenant relationship occurs when the party (e.g. landlord) that decides the level of energy efficiency, is not the party (e.g. tenant) that pays the energy bills. In a well-functioning market, the rent of more energy efficient dwelling should be higher than the rent of a less energy-efficient dwelling. The landlord may not be able to recover the additional capital costs from the party that enjoys the energy savings (e.g. by increasing the rent), because he finds it difficult to convey information on the energy efficiency characteristics of the dwelling which are difficult to observe. Furthermore, in many countries are not allowed to raise the rent unless the tenant changes. The landlord may thus decide to under-invest in energy efficiency (Jaffe et al, 2004; Giraudet et al, 2012).

2.2.2.2. Asymmetric information

“Information asymmetry is typically assumed to be a market failure, and is studied under the paradigm of traditional economics” (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 13).

The optimal contract in the situation where a principal contracts an agent to install some energy efficiency in a setting where the effort exerted by the agent is verifiable (Andersen & Bleischwitz, 2009, p. 7)

- Moral Hazard is the situation where a principal hires an agent to install some energy efficiency and where the effort exerted by the agent to look for the best performing techniques is no longer verifiable;
- Adverse Selection is the situation where a principal is contracting an agent to exert an effort to increase the energy efficiency but does not know the agents ability, skills etc.; and as such the principal does not know which contract to offer the agent. This problem also refers to Akerlof's (1970) so-called “Lemons model”.

2.2.2.2.1. Adverse selection

Information problems occur when the information between two parties engaged in the transaction is asymmetric, potentially leading to adverse selection. The producers or seller of energy-efficiency technologies are generally more informed about the energy performance of the technology, but cannot convince buyers of the benefits of the energy-efficiency investment (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

For example, sellers of energy-efficiency technologies are unable to transfer this information to customers, as some product characteristics related to energy efficiency cannot be observed ex ante. Customers might thus not fully take energy efficiency characteristics into consideration in their purchase decisions (Howarth & Sanstad, 1995).

Buyers know that different products (buildings, equipment, appliances) have different levels of energy efficiency, but these differences are costly to observe. The consumers are thus not willing to pay more for products that are in fact more energy efficient. This in effect resembles Akerlof's (1970) “lemons” model (Alcott et al, 2012). For instance, a renter evaluating a set of different dwellings may be aware that there is a distribution of wall insulation quality and thus of resulting heating costs, but he will not be willing to pay more for a well-insulated dwelling without taking the time to inspect the insulation (id., ibid).

2.2.2.2.2. Moral Hazard

“Moral hazard problems arise when one or several contracting parties take actions that are not fully observable to the others, but impact the final outcomes of the transaction” (Giraudet et al, 2012, p.1).

For instance, when the actions of the contractors (i.e. installers of energy-saving technologies) are not fully observable, contractors will underprovide quality. A homeowner willing to insulate the walls in his dwelling may be motivated by reducing energy consumption, as well as by ancillary attributes such as aesthetics or acoustic comfort. If the homeowner cannot observe the energy efficiency performance of the work done by the contractor, and he anticipates that the contractor is aware of this limitation, he will expect the contractor to save on costs and complete a low quality job. Research results demonstrate that the contractor will indeed underprovide quality (Giraudet et al, 2012, p. 1).

Contractors may thus provide low quality services. Consumers may use high hurdle (discount) rates for energy efficiency investments to insulate themselves from this risk (Giraudet & Houde, 2014).

Moral hazard is unlikely to be an energy efficiency barrier (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 22). For instance, if tenants with energy-inclusive rental agreements keep indoor temperatures higher, landlords are more likely to invest in energy efficiency equipment or to decouple rental agreements and energy use.

2.2.2.3. Empirical evidence for Principal-Agent problems

Empirical evidence has confirmed the existence of the Principal–Agent problem (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 21). Evidence also support the hypothesis that Information asymmetries exist in housing markets (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 23). Busse (2013) however claims that there is little evidence of asymmetric information *in any context* (and even less so in the context of energy efficiency), although he concedes that asymmetric information *may* explain utility-included rents.

According to Brechling & Smith (1994), ownership is the single socio-economic factor that, together with structural characteristics of the dwelling, has a significant effect on the likelihood of investing in energy efficiency technologies

Levinson and Nieman, 2004, p 51-57) provide an example of moral hazard. Apartments are on average kept warmer in winter by households when the contracts include heating expenses in the rental cost, compared to apartments where the tenants pay for heat. The result is based on probit and OLS regression models, using data of the Residential Energy Consumption Survey (RECS) and the American Housing Survey. They assume that landlords include utilities in rental prices even when dwelling units are individually metered, possible because landlords with energy-efficient units cannot credibly communicate this information and instead include utilities as a signal of the dwelling units' efficiency.

Murtishaw & Sathaye (2006) attempted to quantify the magnitude of Principal-Agent problems related to the energy consumption of household appliances in the U.S.. If the individual paying the energy bill is not the individual using the appliance, the user may consume more energy than he would if he had to pay the bill himself. If the individual paying the energy bill is not the person choosing the appliance, the buyer of the appliance will in general choose among the cheapest and often least energy efficient alternatives. They claim that 35% of U.S. residential energy consumption may be affected by the Principal-Agent problem.

An IEA (2007) study finds that Principal-Agent problems and split incentives in the Netherlands may affect 40% of the energy consumed in office buildings; and 41% of the energy used for heating in the residential sector. Furthermore, split incentives in the Netherlands may affect 15% of the energy consumed in the commercial sector.

Schleich & Gruber (2008) claim that Principal-Agent problems and imperfect information are the most important energy-efficiency barrier in samples of the residential sector and 19 sub-sectors of the commercial sector.

Davis (2012) compared the market penetration of efficient appliances between home-owners and renters. Renters, when controlling for income and other variables, are less likely to buy energy-efficient refrigerators, clothes washers and dishwasher. The study found a difference between 1 and 10 percentage points between the shares of owners and renters. The study is based on a linear probability model, using data from the U.S. Residential Energy Consumption Survey (RECS).

Maruejols and Young (2011) provide another example of moral hazard. Tenants in multi-family buildings who do not directly pay for heating are more likely to set higher temperatures. Their result is based on data from the Household Energy Use Survey in Canada.

Gillingham, Harding and Rapson (2012) find that owner-occupied dwelling in California are 20% more likely to be insulated in the attic or ceiling and 13% more likely to be insulated in the exterior walls than renter-occupied dwellings. Tenants who directly pay for energy (i.e. their energy costs are not included in the rent as a lump sum) are 16% more likely to adjust the heating settings at night than tenants who sign energy-inclusive rental agreements. The latter is another example of moral hazard. The results of Gillingham et al. are based on a survey (the California Statewide Residential Appliance Saturation Study) by the California Energy Commission. The data are obtained from a large sample of households.

Choi and Kim (2012, p. 35–36) argue that landlords may use utility-included rental contracts to attract renters or as a signal of other unobservable forms of quality unrelated to energy efficiency. They find an empirical correlation between how well-maintained a unit is and the inclusion of utilities in rent provides.

According to Phillips (2012, p. 118–121), New Zealand tenants stated that they would be willing to pay higher rents in exchange for improved energy efficiency. Respondents' willingness to pay in many cases appears to justify landlord investments in energy-efficiency improvements. However, it appears that landlords do not make such seemingly profitable investments.

Papineau (2014, p. 23–24) surprisingly finds little evidence of asymmetric information between commercial building owners and prospective buyers or tenants.

Ameli & Brandt (2014) report that owners are more likely to invest than renters for the majority of energy-efficiency technologies. The Principal-Agent effect is larger for relatively immobile energy-efficiency investments, for example thermal insulation or windows.

2.2.3. Learning-by-using spillovers

Consumers learn about the benefits of a given energy-efficiency technology by adopting and experiencing it. The adopters of an energy efficient technology thus generate knowledge about the product by using it. Other consumers gain free information about the existence, characteristics and performance of the energy efficiency technology, without having adopted the product themselves. This is the so-called positive “learning-by-using spillover”. Each consumer has an incentive to delay the adoption of the energy efficiency technology in order to learn from other end-users. In other words, each end-user has an incentive to “free ride” (Auffhammer, 2013; Gerarden et al, 2015).

Empirical evidence concerning the ‘learning-by-using spillover’ barrier is limited. (Auffhammer, 2013). “There is limited evidence regarding how information spillovers affect energy-efficiency technology, and – if positive spillovers exist – whether consumers respond by free-riding” (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 23).

A study of thermal insulation choices by homebuilders found no evidence that they learn from the adoption of these technologies by others (Jaffe & Stavins, 1995).

The “learning-by-using spillover” barrier is related to theoretical research that highlights the potential for “social learning” to lead to inefficient technology adoptions.

2.3. ENERGY MARKET FAILURES

2.3.1. Why energy prices matter

The discounted value of the expected savings in energy costs $NPV_{savings}$ depends on the price of energy P_{energy} . For instance, the relevant energy price in case of an investment in an air conditioning (AC) system would be the price of electricity. The relevant price in the case of purchasing an internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicle would be the price of the appropriate transportation fuel, e.g. gasoline / petrol, diesel, LPG or compressed natural gas (CNG). The benefit of an energy-efficiency technology is that it leads to a reduction in energy use Δe (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 8). The higher the price of

energy tied to the energy-efficiency technology, the larger the payoffs from investing in that energy-efficiency technology.

The energy price levels are relevant because they set the expected magnitude of the avoided cost from buying the energy-efficiency technology. Low energy prices in itself are not a market failure, but there are “energy market failures” that lead to a difference between the energy price that consumers face and the energy price that society faces (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 8).

2.3.1.1. Unpriced externalities

Negative externalities are social costs of decisions that are not internalized by the economic agents making those decisions. Examples are emissions of CO₂, particulate matter, SO₂ or NO_x; the water temperature increase by cooling towers, etc. (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 9). Negative externalities are a source of underinvestment in energy efficiency technologies from a social perspective. Energy prices do not reflect the true marginal social cost of energy consumption, as they do not include the environmental costs associated with burning fossil fuels (Ameli & Brandt, 2015). Without internalizing the negative externalities the energy prices are too low; and they do not send the appropriate signals to consumers (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 9). In other words, consumers do not have an economic incentive to minimize the external cost; so they over-consume energy and do not adopt energy-efficiency technologies (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

2.3.1.2. Energy price regulation

Another energy market failure are the incorrect relative prices in markets for energy. For example, distributed generators in distributed electric power system may not pay their proportional network charges whenever volumetric charges and net metering are jointly applied. Regulators may impose regulated tariffs that exceed the true costs or that cross-subsidize some types of consumers at the expense of others. For example, residential customers may be cross-subsidizing commercial and industrial customers in some countries. The presence of market power by energy providers tends to increase the prices that consumers face (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 9).

The energy price signal may thus become ineffective because regulators keep energy prices artificially low or cross-subsidize certain consumer segments. If the regulated energy prices are set below the marginal costs of generation, transmission and distribution, particularly for peak loads, then the regulators “... set prices and deliver bills that make it difficult for consumers to adjust their behaviour and value energy saving technologies” (Cooper, 2013, p. 2).

There may be strong evidence that residential customers respond to the average price of electricity rather than marginal price of electricity. This matters, because marginal prices are generally greater than the average prices (Ito, 2014; Palmer, 2013).

2.3.2. The true social cost of energy

From the perspective of the consumer, the decision to invest in an energy-efficiency technology depends on the private cost of energy. From the perspective of society, the decision to invest in an energy-efficiency technology should depend on the true social cost of energy. The social cost may be larger (or smaller) than the private cost (Knittel et al, 2014).

Policy instruments addressing some of the energy market failures include:

- A pigouvian tax (e.g. an „energy tax“ or a „carbon tax“) to incorporate environmental externalities, by adding the equivalent of the external cost of emission to the energy price. “The resulting internalisation provides an incentive for customers to reduce their energy consumption and to adopt more energy saving measures“ (Ameli & Brandt, 2015, p. 11);
- Congestion pricing, to provide a more efficient price signal for the consumption of transportation fuels.

2.4. CAPITAL MARKET FAILURES

2.4.1. Access to capital

2.4.1.1. Liquidity constraint

Limited or constrained access to capital may inhibit cost-effective energy efficiency measures from being implemented (Hirst & Brown, 1990; Jaffe & Stavins, 1994). The lack of access to capital is one of the major barriers to capital intensive investments, including investments in energy-efficiency technologies (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

Energy-efficiency technologies generally have high(er) upfront investment costs. The cost to upgrade a building's envelope, the cost of energy-efficient equipment (e.g. heating, cooling, and ventilation installations, lighting systems, etc.) represent a substantial upfront investment and may require debt financing. If end-users do not have liquidity ("liquidity constraint") to invest in profitable energy efficiency technologies, they will need to borrow money. Capital markets in those circumstances emerge as enablers of energy-efficiency technology diffusion (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 14).

Households would be expected to invest in any profitable (energy-efficiency) technology, independently of their income, if they have (unlimited) access to capital (Ameli & Brandt, 2015). Capital markets may be imperfect. "Many consumers have access to capital only at costs well above the average rate of return on capital in the economy" (Cagno et al, 2013, p. 292). Potential investors facing credit constraints may be unable to finance energy-efficiency investments, even if future returns justify the upfront costs. This could result in an implicit discount rate above normal market rates (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 30). The "lack of access to capital" barrier may be particularly critical for low income households and for some SMEs or cash-constrained industries (Cagno et al, 2013, p. 292; Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

If access to capital is limited, then end-users may not be able to invest even if the discounted energy savings over the lifetime of the technology outweigh the initial investment costs (Ameli & Brandt, 2015). The end-users who do not get credit will not invest (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 14).

2.4.1.2. Reasons

Literature gives a number of reasons for the existence of capital market failures.

Golovo & Eto (1996) view the "lack of access to capital" barrier as an information problem (asymmetric information, adverse selection) due to the cost entailed in investigating the credit worthiness of individuals and small firms. Financial institutions will not factor the energy consuming characteristics of energy saving durables into their calculations. Lenders are unable to assess the profitability of the investment in terms of future savings; and thus the likelihood of repayment by borrowers. The investors with the most profitable investments may withdraw first.

Weller (2007) provides evidence that access to capital is particularly limited for low-income households, who are less likely to meet lenders' criteria for a specific loan

"Energy Service Providers" or ESCoPs guarantee the energy performance of the energy-efficiency investment, sometimes providing the financing themselves, sometimes sharing the profits of energy savings with the end-users. The ESCoP pays for the difference if the guaranteed energy savings in the EPC (energy performance contract) do not materialize. ESCoPs are not interested in the residential market, because the potential energy savings for a project are small compared to the transaction costs, especially when ownership of buildings is dispersed over many private owners. ESCoPs limit their activities to the (national, regional and local) public and institutional markets. (Satchwell et al, 2010; Grim, 2005; Zabler & Hatcher, 2003).

A survey in the U.S. reports that only a small fraction (6.5%) of households use home equity loans to finance energy retrofits. Palmer et al.(2011) claim that this reluctance may be due to credit constraints.

Credit constraints for energy-efficiency investments in the building sector may be more severe than for other types of investments. Financial institutions (banks) often lack know-how to measure and verify energy savings, which depend on building types and construction periods amongst other variables (Saheb et al, 2012; Palmer et al, 2012)

Palmer et al (2012) focus on the costs of loans. The small size of unsecured loans for small energy efficiency investments in the residential market, and given (high) fixed administrative costs (initial fee), make these loans very costly for end users. The small volume of these types of loans make them unprofitable for lenders. Palmer et al. also invoke the “asymmetric information, adverse selection” barrier. Lenders cannot distinguish ex ante between low-risk and high-risk borrowers. Banks increase interest rates to protect themselves against losses from high-risk borrowers. Low-risk borrowers consequently withdraw from the market, even if banks could lend to them at a profit if they offer lower rates (Palmer et al, 2012).

2.4.1.3. Empirical evidence

Empirical evidence regarding the importance of credit constraints for energy-efficiency investments is scarce (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

Hausman (1979) estimated a discrete choice model using 65 observations of consumer choices between air conditioner models, which varied in upfront cost and energy efficiency rating. The implicit discount rate that consumers use to decide on the investments in air-conditioners decreases exponentially with income. This is likely due to liquidity constraints, as middle and low-income households seem to take up highly profitable energy efficiency investments.

A study by Ameli and Brandt (2014) based on the “Evidence from the OECD Survey on Household Environmental Behaviour and Attitudes” found that investments generally depend positively on income (with the exception of light bulbs, solar panels and heat pumps). An increase in income leads to a large increase in the (predicted) probability to invest for low-income levels; but this marginal impact of higher income decreases with income and levels of for high-income levels. The initial upfront costs of energy-efficiency technologies is a significant barrier for low-income households who may lack access to capital. The empirical analysis is based on the estimation of binary logit regression models.

2.4.2. Constraints other than liquidity constraints

Limited access to capital may also arise due to restrictions on lending money (Hirst and Brown, 1990).

Loss of consumer confidence might detract investment from profitable projects even in the presence of perfectly functioning capital markets. as agents might not want to acquire more debt (Brown, 2004).

2.5. INNOVATION MARKET FAILURES

Innovation market failures consist of:

- Innovation spill-over effects, e.g. R&D spill-overs or Learning-by-doing spill-overs;
- Inefficient product differentiation due to market power;
- Inefficient introduction of new products due to consumer demand (taste) spill-overs.

Innovation spillovers, such as R&D spillovers and learning-by-doing spillovers, can be classified as innovation market failures (Busse, 2013).

2.5.1. R&D spillovers

Research & development (R&D) spill-over is the excess of the social rate of return over the private rate of return of the innovating firm. Firms that develop or adopt energy efficiency technologies absorb the market and technological risks associated with it, but the payback and benefits, while benefiting the firm involved, also flow to the public, competitors and other parts of the economy indirectly. These positive externalities may mean that private firms will invest less or at a slower rate in (energy efficiency) innovation than is socially desirable (Chai & Yeo, 2012).

There seems to be minimal evidence for the existence of R&D spillovers specific to energy efficiency (Busse, 2013).

2.5.2. Inefficient product differentiation due to market power

For equal attributes, the energy efficient version of a product should be perceived as higher quality by buyers and will generally require higher quality (costlier) inputs (Busse, 2013).

A multi-product monopolist may distort the array of quality towards either the high end or the low end, for price discrimination reasons. For instance, firms with market power have an incentive to under-supply – relative to the social optimum – products with a given attribute –such as energy efficiency – to end-users with the lowest willingness-to-pay (WTP) for that particular attribute, in order to charge higher margins on products aimed at end-users with a higher valuation of that attribute. This may lead to a limited availability (market supply) of energy efficient technologies (at the low end).

For example, Fischer (2010) models how automobile manufacturers might manipulate the fuel economy to differentiate its product line, segment consumers, and thus obtain higher prices for its fleet of vehicles.

It is unclear whether there are issues related to the variety, availability, and pricing of energy-efficient products, as distinct from many other types of products (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 4).

2.5.3. Inefficient introduction of new products due to consumer demand spillovers

Whenever there is a radical innovation, there may be an initial period akin to a loss-leader period in which manufacturers must make costly investments in order to overcome consumer reluctance. Producers who invest in getting consumers over this reluctance may not capture the full benefits of having done so. Benefits may spill over to their competitors. Markets may thus be over-conservative in introducing new energy efficient alternatives because it takes money to get consumer adoption of the new technology (Busse, 2013).

3. BEHAVIOURAL FAILURES

3.1. INTRODUCTION TO BEHAVIOURAL FAILURES

3.1.1. Definitions

Traditional economics assumes individuals always behave rationally (Pollit et al, 2011).

“Experimental settings and empirical observations indicate that behaviour deviates systematically from what traditional models would predict” (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 2).

Some economists propose that systematic “behavioural biases” in consumer decision making may explain the apparent energy efficiency gap (for instance, Allcott, Mullainathan & Taubinsky, 2014; or Tietenberg, 2009).

Behavioural economics argues that the classic view of consumers as market agents that maximize their overall utility may not be a good representation of actual consumer behaviour (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 9). Behavioural economists stress the “irrational” aspect of decision making, often referred to as “behavioural failures” (Pollit et al, 2011).

Shogren and Taylor (2008) use the term “behavioural failures” for all those situations in which the consumer does not behave according to rational choice theory.

Gillingham & Palmer (2014, p. 23) distinguish between “behavioural anomaly” and “behavioural failure”:

- Behavioural anomaly refers to consumer behaviour that appears to depart from the standard assumptions of economic theory:
- Behavioural failure refers to anomalies that lead to a systematic differences between „decision utility“ and „experienced utility“. Decision utility is the utility consumers maximize at the time of the choice. Experienced utility is the utility consumers later experience due to the prior decision (Kahneman 1994; Kahneman, Wakker & Sarin 1997).

It would appear that most, but not all, behavioural anomalies are behavioural failures; with possibly two exceptions: reference dependent preferences and non-standard beliefs (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014),

Gillingham and Palmer (2014) view the “...current state of the behavioural welfare economics literature as an important foundation for future research, but the existing theoretical work appears to be far from ready for use in practical policy analysis” (id., ibid, p. 28). For instance, they argue that behavioural economics have thus far avoided the fundamental question of how to reconcile revealed preference theory with the existence of behavioural failures (for example, Allcott and Greenstone 2012; Allcott, Mullainathan & Taubinsky 2014).

3.1.2. Taxonomy

There are many typologies of behavioural failures.

Some of the typologies depend on the theory considered to explain these failures (Ramos et al, 2015). The foremost ones are Bounded rationality (Simon, 1955); Prospect theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979); and Regret theory (Loomes and Sugden, 1982).

Gillingham & Palmer (2014) divide the behavioural anomalies into 3 categories:

- Nonstandard decision-making. These anomalies include limited attention, framing of choices, and suboptimal decision choices;
- Nonstandard preferences. These anomalies include self-control problems (hyperbolic discounting), reference dependence and social preference;
- Nonstandard beliefs.

Ramos et al (2015) list 18 major behavioural failures, divided into two main types:

- Deviations from the Rational Theory of Choice (RTC);
- Biases when dealing with uncertainty.

We propose the (preliminary) taxonomy shown in the following figure.

Figure 3 Taxonomy of behavioural barriers

3.2. NON-STANDARD CALCULATIONS

3.2.1. Bounded rationality (cognitive limitations)

Consumers fail to behave as predicted by rational choice theory (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

Decisions are not based on perfect information and complete rationality. Decisions are often made in constrained environments that result in “bounded” (limited or “non-optimal”) decisions. Individuals are rational but subject to certain cognitive constraints in processing information (Simon, 1986). These limitations make consumers move away from perfectly unbounded optimal resource allocation (Knittel et al, 2014).

Experiments reveal that individuals often make choices that deviate from the assumptions in traditional economics, where decision-makers use concepts of statistical sampling and statistical rules for updating the profit abilities of future events (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 6).

Calculating the “optimal” quantity of energy efficiency for a specific household is relatively complex, so the cognitive costs of performing that optimisation are high. As such, many consumers will base their decisions on simple rules of thumb, which reduce the cognitive load. This is known as bounded rationality (Gerarden et al, 2015). Bounded rationality may prevent consumers from correctly estimating the future energy performance of buildings; heating, cooling or ventilation equipment; lighting systems; appliances; or vehicles (Ramos et al, 2015).

3.2.1.1. Manifestations of bounded rationality

Manifestations of bounded rationality are choice overload; heuristic decision making; and the failure to assess statistical probabilities (Pollit et al, 2011). The most relevant failures are:

- Under uncertainty consumers systematically violate the axiom of rational choice;
- An individual's ability to acquire and absorb disparate pieces of information is limited (Simon, 1959; Tversky & Kahneman, 1981);
- Decision-makers apply simplified decision-making processes, by using only a subset of the available information for complex decisions or applying simple decision rules, called heuristics (Wilson and Dowlatabadi 2007; Della Vigna 2009).

3.2.1.1.1. Choice overload

Individuals find it difficult to make a choice when presented with too many options. Traditional economics assumes that more choices are always preferred to fewer choices (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 5). Gillingham and Palmer (2014) claim that heuristics may play a major role in decision making when there are many variants of a product (for example, vehicles) to choose from (id, ibid., p. 26). This is confirmed by Knittel et al. (2014), who state that given numerous investment opportunities or an overload of information, consumers may rely on heuristics that yield non-optimal decisions.

3.2.1.1.2. Heuristics

Heuristics are shortcuts to decision making, for instance simplistic empirical "rules of thumb". Sanstad and Howarth (1994) claim that decisions are made by rule of thumb. Consumers may use these so-called rules of thumb or heuristics to simplify the decision-making process (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 26). Simon (1955) suggested that individuals adapt known methods to solve new problems, even if the known methods are not optimal for the new situation. This may be the optimal strategy, as it avoids the effort of analysing the new situation.

Decision-makers may thus evaluate an investment on the basis of current prices without incorporating an expectation on future prices (Knittel et al, 2014). This observation is echoed by Pollit et al. In an energy efficiency context, households may use current energy prices to calculate expected savings from an energy efficiency investment, thus not taking into account future energy price increases (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 15).

Wilson & Dowlatabadi (2007) refer to "recognition heuristics" and "elimination heuristics":

- Recognition heuristics refer to a situation where decision-makers favour familiar choices, i.e. they select the option that was chosen last time;
- Elimination heuristics refer to a situation where decision-makers immediately reject alternatives with a particular attribute, for example the most expensive alternatives.

Mental accounting is where consumers categorize purchases under different categories (for example high one-off expenditures versus multiple smaller expenses) and have different discount rates for these categories (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 6). The willingness to spend earned income, windfall income or saved income differs (Thaler, 1999). Mental accounting contradicts the assumption of traditional economics that money is fungible.

The cognitive responses of individuals depend on the way the decision is framed (Kahneman, 1974). Framing of choices means that the way in which choices are framed can affect choices by focusing attention on different subsets of the information being presented (Bernatzi and Thaler, 2002; Duflo et al, 2006). The possibility to "prime" a specific response to a given choice by strategically framing the context is a powerful persuasion technique in marketing. However, most individuals still respond differently to different contexts, in spite of some "hard-wired" responses (Jackson, 2005).

3.2.1.1.3. Failure to assess statistical probabilities

Research indicates that individuals do not correctly process statistical information and probabilities. (Pollit et al, 2011). Individuals tend to overstate small probabilities of catastrophic losses or large gains (Knittel et al, 2014).

3.2.1.2. Empirical evidence of bounded rationality

Consumers' decision processes cannot be directly observed. Cognitive limitations could manifest themselves in the use of heuristics or simple optimization errors (Gerarden et al, 2025, p. 28). However, there is no unified theory of decision-making subject to cognitive limitations from which to draw testable hypotheses (Conlisk, 1996).

Archer et al (1987, p.78) in a study of solar technology adoption find that “*information indispensable to even gross cost calculations was, in fact, absent*” in end-user’s assessments”.

A survey by Kempton and Montgomery (1982) found that consumers use simple heuristics to assess their energy consumption, leading to systematic underinvestment in energy efficiency. Even consumers who understand technical energy measurements make systematic errors (underestimates) in quantifying the benefits of energy efficiency. It might therefore be concluded that even if consumers are provided with technically correct information, and are sophisticated enough to understand it, they may still under-invest in energy efficiency (Defra, 2006).

Friedman and Hauser (1988) find that consumers use average energy prices to estimate the total monthly energy bill, independently of the tiered-rate structure of electricity prices. Households over-consume energy with increasing block rates, because they underestimate energy savings when total volumes consumed are high. Friedman (2002) tested this model by using monthly consumption and billing data from 7,000 households and found that a bounded rationality model explained this behaviour better than one based on utility maximization.

Kempton et al (1992) found that consumers systematically miscalculate payback periods for air conditioners.

Turrentine and Kurani (2007) allude to the role of heuristics in vehicle-purchasing decisions. However, there is no empirical evidence in the context of energy efficiency (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 26).

Consumers systematically misperceive the information contained in fuel economy ratings, due to the inverse relationship between gasoline consumption and miles per gallon. People take an efficiency metrics such as MPG and subtract them to estimate energy savings, which ignores the reciprocal relation to consumption. For instance, subtracting MPG leads end-users to underestimate fuel savings when moving from 16 to 20 MPG; and to overestimate fuel savings when moving from 35 to 50 MPG. This is also known as the “MPG illusion” (for example, Larrick and Soll, 2008; or Allcott, 2013). For the MPG illusion we also refer to the “**lack of information**” barrier. All energy consumption metrics (as well as costs and emissions metrics) for energy-efficiency technologies should be made linear.

Camilleri & Larrick (2014) show that the metric and scale of information provided on energy labels influences the stated preferences for cars of various efficiencies. For example, in a study of hypothetical choices, respondents showed a greater interest in energy efficient vehicles when costs of driving were scaled over 100,000 miles rather than over 100 miles. Information on energy consumption has to be expanded to larger scales (see also **salience**). In that respect, there may be a problem with smart meters, as cost of electricity per hour is negligible.

Ungemach et al. (2013) reveal that translations of the fuel economy of energy efficient cars into multiple perfectly correlated metrics (such as gallon per mile, estimated annual fuel costs and GHG rating) change the stated preferences. People do not spontaneously use gas/petrol consumption as an indication of annual fuel costs or environmental impacts, so this (energy efficiency) attribute has to be “translated” to the end objectives of cost and emissions.

3.2.2. Time-inconsistent preferences

Preferences are time-consistent when decisions are independent of when they are taken. This means that the future will be discounted at a fixed rate, independent of when costs and benefits actually occur (Gintis, 2000).

Self-control problems are situations in which consumers appear to have time-inconsistent preferences (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 24).

3.2.2.1. Consequences of time-inconsistent preferences

Individuals do not make decisions independent of when they are taken. Their discount rate for the same event increases as the event approaches (Harris and Laibson 2001, Frederick et al., 2002, Della Vigna 2009). A time-varying discount rate implies that the time preferences of an individual reverse at some point in the future. If the time between two future rewards diminishes, then the preference between the two future rewards can reverse in favour of the more proximate reward (Pollit et al, 2011). “Consumers appear to take a long-term view of decisions about outcomes that will occur in the distant future, but as the future approaches, the discount rate used to evaluate decisions increases” (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 24). This is inconsistent with exponential discounting used by neoclassical economics (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 4).

There are different ways to represent time-inconsistent preferences.

The model of Gul and Pesendorfer (2001) uses an axiomatic approach to emphasize preferences over sets of alternatives.

Quasi-hyperbolic or (β, δ) preferences are often used to represent time-inconsistent preferences. A quasi-hyperbolic preference model presents discounted utility U_t at time t as the following function of the per-period utility: $U_t = u_t + \beta\delta u_{t+1} + \beta\delta^2 u_{t+2} + \dots$, with δ is the standard discount factor and where $\beta \leq 1$ captures the self-control problems. $\beta = 1$ implies the standard model of discounting.

Hyperbolic discounting is one mathematical way of modelling “time inconsistent discounting”. Under hyperbolic discounting, individuals have higher discount rates for short horizons, but low discount rates for long horizons. They will make short-sighted decisions if costs or benefits are immediate; and far-sighted if both costs and benefits occur in the future (Camerer & Loewenstein, 2004). In the neoclassical model, time preferences are time consistent. Consumers use the same discount rate when comparing time period 1 to time period 2 as they use when comparing time period 100 to time period 101. “Hyperbolic discounting” entails that consumers may instead use a higher discount rate when comparing period 1 to 2, than they would when comparing period 100 to 101. It implies that decision-makers have a near-term bias (Knittel et al, 2014). With an intertemporal choice under hyperbolic discounting the later event is discounted more than the earlier event (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014). That is, “Individuals have a high discount rate for future cost savings, but a small discount rate for large initial investment outlay” (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 14).

3.2.2.2. Empirical evidence

Tsvetanov & Segerson (2013), using the Gul and Pesendorfer self-control framework, empirically show that household refrigerator choices appear consistent with time-inconsistent preferences. Consumers may appear to be willing to adopt energy-efficient investments in the future. Their inclination to do so however vanishes as the investment event approaches, because they discount future benefits more strongly with the cost incurred before.

3.3. BEHAVIOURAL BIAS

3.3.1. Inattentiveness – Salience

3.3.1.1. Inattention or inattentiveness

Consumers appear to be inattentive. Individuals have limited attention, leading them to systematically underweight certain information (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014). Consumers will presumably only allocate attention to an attribute if the cognitive costs of doing so are less than the expected utility gains (Howarth & Andersson, 1993; Sallee, 2013).

In an energy efficiency context, Gillingham and Palmer (2014) point out that limited attention may lead consumers to systematically underestimate the future fuel savings from a more energy-efficient product. In the words of Allcott et al. (2012), “It seems possible that some consumers might be inattentive

to energy efficiency when purchasing energy-using durable goods” (id., *ibid.*, p. 22). Gerarden et al. (2015) likewise state that consumers are inattentive to energy costs.

Knittel et al. (2014) elucidate that a variety of factors enter into the purchase of an energy-intensive product. For instance, the consumer buying a refrigerator weights the utility benefits of such attributes as size, appearance, features such as through-the-door ice dispensing, etc. A consumer may have a finite amount of attention available, and therefore focus on other product attributes ignoring those that affect energy efficiency (id, *ibid.*, p. 12-13). Stern & Aronson (1984) argue that consumers do not conceptualize and energy-consuming equipment only as investments. When people buy a car, they are concerned with a variety of attributes including performance, reliability, safety, styling, status, resale value and fuel-efficiency, where the primary focus may be on any of those characteristics (id., *ibid.*, p. 61).

3.3.1.2. Salience

The salience effect is when individuals tend to weigh information in proportion to its vividness and give more importance to easily observable factors (Yates and Aronson, 1993).

Ramos et al, (2015) suggest that bounded rationality may lead consumers to consider only the most salient or familiar features when choosing among the many attributes of a building; heating, cooling or ventilation installation, lighting systems, appliance or vehicle. Pollit et al. (2011) are somewhat more explicit by stating that “...individuals place disproportional weight on vivid and observable factors. This tendency may result in placing too much emphasis on initial investment costs, and underinvestment in energy efficiency” (id, *ibid.*, p. 14). Gerarden et al, (2015) similarly remark that energy cost (savings) may not be salient for energy-efficiency investment decisions. This is confirmed by Ameli & Brandt (2015) who postulate that consumers may tend to perceive the upfront cost easily, because it is relatively large and directly observable, while assessing the total value of energy savings over the life of an investment is more difficult given the uncertainty surrounding energy savings and fluctuations in energy prices (id., *ibid.*, p. 19).

3.3.1.3. Empirical evidence

There are two methods for testing inattention to energy efficiency (Gerarden et al, 2015):

- Discrete choice studies. These studies assess the trade-off consumers make between purchase price and future energy operating costs;
- Experimental studies, including belief elicitation. Researchers could elicit stated beliefs along with stated preferences in field experiments that present consumers with actual choices..

Hal (1997) found that consumers largely ignored replacement ink prices when making printer purchase decisions.

According to Allcott (2011) almost 50% of surveyed vehicle buyers report making their decisions without considering fuel costs.

Sallee (2014) estimates that the loss in consumer welfare from being inattentive to fuel economy when purchasing a new vehicle is on the order of \$100 - \$200 per purchase. If the cost of information exceeds this, then consumers will rationally ignore fuel economy during their purchase decision.

3.3.2. Myopia – short-sightedness

3.3.2.1. Definition

Decision-makers make far-sighted decisions when both cost and benefits are in the future; but shift into a short-sighted mind-set when only costs or benefits are immediate. For instance, the average levelized cost of an energy efficiency technology may be much lower than the average energy price, but end-users make a short-sighted decision when faced with the first year investment costs (Knittel et al, 2014, p. 9-10). Biased decision making may lead individuals to give a significantly higher rating to initial investment costs than to future energy savings (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

3.3.2.2. Empirical evidence

Jaffe and Stavins (1995) find that the technology cost effect on investment decisions is nearly three (3) times larger than the energy price effect.

Hasset & Metcalf (1995) on the other hand find that the technology cost effect on investment decisions is not three times but eight (8) times larger than the energy price effect.

According to Anderson and Newell (2004), firms are about 40% more responsive to investment costs than to energy savings.

Ameli and Brandt (2014) observe that a significant fraction of households are less likely to invest in heat thermostats and solar panels at the same time.

Allcott and Wozny (2014) notice that consumers are indifferent between \$0.76 now and \$1.00 of discounted future gasoline expenditures. This result may suggest the possibility of myopia or undervaluation of fuel economy.

3.3.3. Prospect theory: reference points – loss aversion – status-quo bias

3.3.3.1. Manifestations of prospect theory

In standard economic theory, the preferences of an individual are independent from the composition of his current endowment (assets) or his current consumption (Pollit et al, 2011). “Reference-dependent preferences refer to a situation of decision making under uncertainty where the consumer’s utility from any outcome depends on the outcome’s relationship to a particular reference point” (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 24). Prospect theory states that welfare changes should be evaluated according to certain reference points (Kahnemann & Tversky, 1979). Reference points are like a lens through which consumers evaluate reality and put everything within its context (Knittel et al, 2014).

Manifestations of prospect theory are “loss aversion”, “the endowment effect” and “status quo bias”.

3.3.3.1.1. Loss aversion

Individuals normally perceive outcomes as losses and gains relative to a reference point, usually the status quo (Ameli & Brandt, 2015). According to traditional economics individuals are either risk neutral or risk averse, but they place the same value on losses and gains of the same amount. The “reflection effect” is the phenomenon where the valuation of losses is the mirror image of the valuation of gains. According to prospect theory, a decision-maker exhibits the reflection effect when he is risk-averse in the face of potential gains, but he is risk-seeking in the face of potential loss (Pollit et al, 2011). In other words, individuals exhibit loss aversion in decision-making under uncertainty, giving much more weight to a loss than to an equivalent uncertain gain. Loss aversion can partly explain why consumers do not take up profitable investments, as they weight the certain initial costs (the loss) much more strongly than future uncertain benefits, even if these are in principle of an equivalent value (Ameli & Brandt, 2015, p. 19). Consumers might thus be focusing more in the extra investment required to purchase the energy-efficiency technology than on the future reductions of energy consumption (Knittel et al, 2014). The importance of loss aversion increases with the volatility in energy prices (Greene, 2011).

It is important to note that **inertia** may be an equally valid explanation for many phenomena attributable to loss aversion (Gal, 2006).

3.3.3.1.2. Endowment effect

The endowment effect refers to the extra value that individuals attach to goods they already own or services they already receive (Pollit et al, 2011). The endowment point is the reference point, and agents have a kink in the valuation around that point (Thaler, 1980). The endowment effect may explain why consumers are not willing to replace their standard products even if it is economical efficient to do so (Knittel et al, 2014). “Households are attached to the appliances they currently own, and are not willing to replace them, even if it is efficient to do so” (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 14). These effects should lose importance as energy-efficiency technologies increase their market presence and consumers understand that (in principle) they offer the same utility as standard technologies (id., ibid).

3.3.3.1.3. Status-quo bias

Decision-makers tend to have status-quo bias. Status-quo bias is the phenomenon where individuals when in doubt tend to stick to the default option chosen for them (Pollit et al, 2011). To the extent that standard technologies are still considered the default option, consumers can be expected to be biased away from energy efficient technologies (Knittel et al, 2014). Status quo bias may limit the potential to actually achieve the estimated energy efficiency potential (Ramos et al, 2015).

3.3.3.2. Empirical evidence

The fact that individuals tend to value losses more than gains has been demonstrated empirically. Contingent valuation studies show that willingness to accept (WTA) is typically higher than willingness to pay (WTP) (Pollit et al, 2011). But in the context of energy efficiency, “*Very little is known about the impacts of loss aversion and reference points on energy-efficiency investments*” (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 27).

Responses in experimental research are partially attributable to changes in reference points (Allcott, 2011; Goldstein, Cialdini & Griskevicius, 2008).

Dinner et al (2011) show in three experiments that replacing incandescent light bulbs with compact fluorescent lamps (CFLs) as the default significantly increased the proportion of subjects who chose CFLs.

Survey evidence on consumer demand for vehicle fuel economy is consistent with loss aversion (Greene, Evans & Hiestand 2013).

Consumers who buy a car have to take into account the uncertainties surrounding future fuel prices, the kilometres the vehicle will be driven and the actual energy performance improvement of the vehicle. Loss aversion implies that they will weigh the potential negative payoffs so heavily that they may not purchase the more expensive energy-efficient vehicle even if it would most likely have positive net benefits (Greene, German & Delucchi, 2009). However, the authors do not provide empirical evidence of loss aversion (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 25).

3.3.4. Anchoring bias

The “anchoring bias” effect is based on research by Attari et al (2010).

Participants in a U.S. survey were asked to estimate the number of energy units used in one hour by certain appliances (e.g. dishwasher), and to estimate the energy savings by different actions (for example changing dishwasher temperature). The reference point was a 100-Watt incandescent bulb using 100 units of energy in one hour. Respondent made reasonably accurate estimates of the amount of energy small devices (CFLs, PCs, stereos, etc.) use; but the estimates for larger or more energy-intensive devices (air conditioners, space heaters, dishwasher, clothes dryers, etc.) the estimates were off by a factor of three or more. Attari et al. (2010) suggests that the result may be caused by an “anchoring bias”. The respondents tend to make estimates as multiples of the implicit metric. The participants’ estimates would be too close to the reference point, which serves as “an anchor”. For larger appliances those adjustments tend to be too small.

3.3.5. Non-standard beliefs

Gillingham and Palmer (2014) put forward non-standard beliefs as a potential behavioural bias that may contribute to the undervaluation of energy savings.

Nonstandard beliefs are systematically incorrect beliefs about the future (Della Vigna, 2009).

Empirical evidence is scarce. Consumer beliefs about future fuel savings from a higher fuel economy vehicle (holding driving behaviour constant) do not match the known true values. It is not clear whether their beliefs are systematically biased (Allcott, 2013).

3.3.6. The magnitude effect – temporal discount rates

The magnitude effect is attributed to Prelec and Loewenstein (1991). Individuals weight events according to the magnitude of the outcome: Decision-makers use:

- a high subjective temporal discount rate for small outcomes;
- a low subjective temporal discount rate for large outcomes.

The magnitude effect might explain the high implicit discount rates observed for energy efficiency investments as energy savings per period are small, while initial costs are large (Ameli & Brandt, 2015, p. 19).

There appears to be no empirical evidence for the magnitude effect in the context of energy efficiency.

3.4. INFORMATION – BEHAVIOURAL ASPECTS

3.4.1. Form of information

3.4.1.1. Definition

Behavioural economics finds that the way the information is presented or framed is also important. Regulators should therefore use information programs to take advantage of psychological features of human decision-making (Alcott & Mullainathan, 2010).

If individuals are affected more by **salient** information rather than merely accurate information, then vivid descriptions and visual clues are important (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 12-13) Thollander et al (2010) focus on the **inattention** aspect: “*Information does not always receive as much attention as anticipated, since people are (often) not active information-seekers but rather selective about attending to and assimilating information*” (id. Ibid., p. 54).

Another important aspect is feedback. For instance, conventional electricity meters provide cumulative consumption information. Consumers do not always know which appliances consume most electricity and when. Feedback should be given on the beneficial consequences of previous energy decisions if subsequent efficiency measures are to be encouraged (Seligman, Becker & Darley, 1981). Providing energy-saving information and energy-consumption feedback may be successful in eliciting behavioural changes (Pollit et al, 2011).

3.4.1.2. Empirical evidence

Research has demonstrated that to increase the diffusion and acceptance of information on cost-effective energy efficiency technologies, the information should be simple, specific, presented in a vivid and personalized manner, and come from a person who is similar to the receiver. If those conditions are met, some individuals are more likely to remember the information (Stern and Aronson, 1984; Palm, 2009; 2010).

3.4.2. Credibility and trust

3.4.2.1. Definition

End-users cannot always easily gain accurate information about the ultimate comparative cost of different energy-efficiency investment options. They will rely on the most credible available information (Thollander et al, 2010, p. 54). The source of information must be considered credible and trustworthy by the receiver in order to successfully deliver information about cost-effective energy efficiency technologies. If these factors are lacking this will result in inefficient choices (Stern & Aronson, 1984). The effective spread of information thus depends on trustworthy information providers (Thollander et al, 2010, p. 55).

Sorrell et al (2010) in their classification of barriers combine credibility and trust, even though they are two distinct aspects of information. The reason is that credibility and trust can hardly be distinguished in empirical research.

3.4.2.2. Empirical evidence

Stern and Aronson (1984) conducted the following experiment. Pamphlets describing how to save energy in home air conditioning systems were sent out to 1,000 households in New York. Fifty percent of

the households received the information in a mailing from the state regulatory agency for utilities, the other half received it from the local electricity utility. The following month, households that had received the pamphlet from the state agency used about 8% less electricity than the households that had received the same pamphlet from the local electricity utility.

3.5. PSYCHOLOGY: INERTIA AND VALUES

3.5.1. Psychological theories

Psychological theories of action that are most often applied to explain different behaviours, including energy efficiency related behaviour, are the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) and the norm-activation model (NAM).

Values are central, but rather distant determinants of human behaviour within the action theories TPB and NAM. Values influence and are mediated by variables such as attitudes and norms which represent more direct and more specific determinants of behaviour. The determinants “attitudes” and “norms” have more explanatory power than “values” to explain specific behaviour and are common components of psychological action theories. Values are useful concepts for holistic lifestyle concepts which are applicable to various fields of behaviour. Lifestyle concepts are a practical means to broaden the micro focus of psychological models to the meso level of social groups (Peters et al, 2012).

3.5.1.1. The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), by including an additional variable known as “Perceived Behavioural Control” (PBC) The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) states that behaviour is directly influenced by an individual’s intention to perform the behaviour.

Figure 4 The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

Source: Jackson (2005).

Intention, in turn, is determined by (Peters et al, 2002):

- an individual’s attitude towards the behaviour, defined as an overall evaluation of its possible consequences;
- subjective norms, referring to the perceived expectations of other important persons, e.g., family, peers, neighbours;

- the perceived behavioural control (PBC), defined as the perceived ease or difficulty with which the individual will be able to perform or carry out the behaviour due to non-motivational factors such as availability of opportunities and resources.

Intention together with PBC may be used to predict actual behaviour, for two reasons (Jackson, 2005):

- The degree of success in carrying out an intention (holding the intention constant) depends on the strength of the individual's belief in his ability to carry out that behaviour;
- PBC is likely to indicate actual behaviour control, assuming the individual's perception of control are not misguided.

TPB has been applied widely to understand behaviour in a vast array of contexts, including energy consumption (Stern, 2000). TPB is not considered useful or effective in relation to planning and designing the type of intervention that will result in behaviour change.

3.5.1.2. The Norm-Activation Model (NAM)

The Norm-activation model (NAM) (Schwartz, 1977) explains behaviour as being influenced by a personal norm to engage in the specific behaviour. The "personal norm" in the Norm-Activation Model (NAM) is noticeably different from the "subjective norm" in the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) or in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB). Personal norms are "feelings of strong moral obligation that individuals experience for themselves to engage in pro-social behaviour". NAM rejects the idea that intention is a mediator between "personal norm" and behaviour. Personal norms are the only direct determinants of pro-social behaviours.

Figure 5 The Norm-Activation Model

Source: Jackson (2005).

Personal norms have to direct psychological antecedents:

- An awareness of the consequences of one's actions;
- The acceptance ("ascription") of the personal responsibility that an individual holds for these consequences.

Awareness and ascription are not only causal antecedent of personal norms, they also moderate the link between "personal norm" and "behaviour" (Jackson, 2005):

- The link is stronger when an individual is aware of the negative consequences of not engaging in pro-social behaviour and accepts responsibility for those consequences;
- The link is weaker when an individual is not aware of negative consequences and denies responsibility.

The relationship between "personal norm" and "behaviour" is often moderated by the existence of external social and institutional constraints.

Empirical research focuses on the correlation between the psychological antecedents ('awareness of consequences' and 'ascription of responsibility') and 'personal norm'; and assumes that existence of the personal norm is sufficient for the behaviour to occur.

Black et al (1995) used the NAM to explain household energy adaptations. Bamberg & Schmidt (2003) used the NAM to explore alternatives to car use.

3.5.2. Inertia – habit and routines

3.5.2.1. Inertia

Inertia represents the resistance to change. Inertia implies that individuals are, in part, creatures of habit and established routines, which may make it difficult to create changes to such behaviours and habits (Thollander et al, 2010, p. 56). The more radical the change, the higher the barrier will be. Inertia can result in preferring quick and low investments and returns (Cagno et al, 2013).

According to Hewett (1998), inertia represents the combined effect of:

- Treating gains differently from losses;
- Giving greater weighting to certain outcomes with respect to those that are uncertain;
- Minimizing the regret.

All three factors may cause individuals to favour the **status quo**.

3.5.2.2. Habit and routines

Expectancy-value models like Rational Choice Theory (RCT) suggest that behaviour is the product of cognitive deliberation. Adjusted expectancy-value models like the Theory of Reasoned Behaviour (TPB) that regard behaviour as being mediated by intention, also presuppose some kind of cognitive deliberation.

It is not the case that individual actions are invariably the result of conscious cognitive deliberation. Individuals often seem to act instinctively; automatically; out of habit or routine; or driven by emotional responses that appear beyond control in particular situations (Jackson, 2005).

Jackson (2005) explains the role of habit and routine as follows:

- Habitual or routine behaviour (e.g. turning the lights on, switching the TV off) is highly automated and requires little cognitive effort. Simple heuristics or automated responses free up cognitive processes for more important decisions;
- Habitual or routine behaviour is particularly successful when decision contexts hardly change. The belief that deliberation would always come up with the same answer is justified in those situations. Habits or routines become problematic when the decision context does change;
- Habits and routines are often re-enforced by short-run incentives, which can outweigh the long-run benefits of a behavioural change.

Habit makes it difficult to adopt new technologies. Individuals are often hesitant to change, which may, in turn, result in the overlooking of cost-effective energy efficiency measure (Stern & Aronson, 1984).

3.5.3. Values and the “value-action gap”

3.5.3.1. The importance of values

Examples of values are the moral commitment to use energy more efficiently; concern for the environment; or helping others. These values may influence individuals and groups of individuals to adopt energy efficiency technologies. Energy efficiency improvements are more likely to be of interest if the organization consists of individuals with real ambition, preferably represented by a key individual within top management (Stern, 1992).

On the other hand: “A lack of values related to energy efficiency may inhibit measures from being undertaken” (Thollander et al, 2010, p. 55). Indeed, the absence in a firm of individuals motivated by environmental values may downgrade energy efficiency as a peripheral issue. It is a behavioural barrier for which energy-efficient technologies may neither be adopted nor promoted (Cagno et al, 2013).

Frey (1999) defines “environmental moral” as the “intrinsic motivation for pro-environmental activity”. He argues that traditional policy instruments such as taxes and tradable permits crowd out “environmental moral. The increase in the price of an activity will not only decrease environmentally harmful behaviour, but it may also decrease the intrinsic motivation for pro-environmental activity.

3.5.3.2. The “Common Cause Approach”

The “Common Cause Approach” is described by [Chatterton \(2011\)](#) as follows. The “Common Cause Approach” focuses on the role of “identity” and “values” in driving decision-making. This includes conscious and sub-conscious impacts on decisions and behaviour. The approach is concerned with problems where it is not in an individual’s immediate self-interest to engage in resolving them, such as climate change. It is necessary to engage people with their values to get them to act in relation to these issues. There are two broad types of values:

- Intrinsic values. These values see certain things as having “inherent worth” (e.g. sense of community);
- Extrinsic values. These values are dependent on the response (e.g. praise or reward) they elicit from others (e.g. social status).

Empirical evidence suggest that intrinsic and extrinsic values operate antagonistically to each other. For instance, if energy savings are promoted as “saving money”, this activates extrinsic values. The value of money comes from ‘what it can buy’, including social status. The message “saving money” may thus suppress intrinsic values, e.g. the wider concern about environmental or social problems. End-users may be less inclined to undertake more expensive energy saving measures, or to buy “green products”.

3.5.3.3. The “value-action” gap or “attitude-behaviour gap”

The “value-action” gap is where individuals’ behaviour seems not closely related to their expressed values. Having pro-environmental values or attitudes and engaging in pro-environmental behaviour are not the same thing. [Gatersleben et al \(2002\)](#) and [Jensen \(2002\)](#) show that pro-environmental intentions do not always correlate with reduced energy consumption in the households. There may even be a negative correlation: households in higher socio-demographic classes often report higher environmental attitudes, but household energy consumption correlates positively with household size (a key indicator of socio-economic class). However, factors other than values, such as “social norms”, “facilitating conditions” and “habits”, etc. also determine actions.

3.5.3.4. Empirical evidence

[Thollander et al. \(2010\)](#) mention two examples where values appear to play an important role:

- A study on showering in a university building by [Aronsson and O’Leary \(1983\)](#) showed that the number of students taking short, energy-saving showers increased from 6% when a sign encouraging short showers was put up; to 19% when an intrusive sign was used; to 49% when the researchers used a student to set an example for others by always turning off the water and soaping up whenever someone came into the facility; and to 67% when two students serving as examples were used ([Thollander et al, 2010, p. 56](#)); .
- In a study of households, [Stern and Aronson \(1984\)](#) find that norms only have a strong impact on *cost-free* energy efficiency and energy conservation measures.

[Ameli and Brandt \(2015\)](#) state that psychological factors correlate with residential energy use, and mention a few studies, including one of their own:

- According to [Guerin et al \(2000\)](#), households’ attitudes such as comfort, health, concern, and environmental knowledge, correlate with the *propensity* to change behaviour. However, households’ characteristics such as age, income, household size, or size of dwelling better predict the actual energy consumption;
- [Olli et al \(2001\)](#) find that environmental knowledge has a positive effect on environmentally responsible behaviour.
- [Ameli & Brandt \(2015\)](#) in their study demonstrate that understanding the causes of climate change does not increase the likelihood to invest, nor the willingness to make compromises to solve environmental problems.

3.5.4. Other psychological factors

Psychological factors other than inertia or value may correlate with energy consumption.

Kempton et al, (1992) state that consumers use air-conditioners for a number of very different reasons, such as health (e.g. arthritis); safety (e.g. never leave the AC on when leaving the room); comfort and differences in physiological characteristics.

3.6. SOCIOLOGY: SOCIALITY AND SELF - PRO-SOCIAL BEHAVIOUR - SOCIAL NORMS

3.6.1. Sociality and self

Individuals often adopt products, not because those items fulfil “utilitarian needs”, but because they are “markers” of “social status” and “social esteem”; as well as of “identity” and “self-concept”. Those factors often supersede economic factors. For example, consumers may pay more for high performance cars, because they communicate aspects of their status and “self-identity” (“who they are relative to others in society”) (Ehrhardt-Martinez & Laitner, 2009)..

3.6.1.1. The Social-Symbolic Self

The individual self, i.e. the personal identity, is an emergent property of inherently social relations (Jackson, 2005).

So-called “social conversations” (Mead, 1956) provide the mechanism for:

- negotiating and internalizing (in personal identity) values, attitudes and beliefs of the social group;
- negotiating and internalising cultural norms.

The school of “symbolic interactionism” (Blumer, 1969) proposes three (3) key premises about human action:

- Individuals respond to material artefacts on the basis of the symbolic meanings that these artefacts carry. Material artefacts carry symbolic significance as well as functional utility. Humans as social beings respond to situations on the basis of symbolic meanings;
- The meaning of those artefacts is negotiated through social interactions. Social conversations mediate individuals’ attitudes and behaviours. The symbolic meanings are socially negotiated and constructed;
- The meanings are handled in and modified by an “interpretative process” specific to the situation and the individuals involved. The interpretative process is not a purely automatic application of established meanings. The socially constructed meanings are continually adapted and transformed in the context of specific situations.

The symbolic meanings of material artefacts or of commodities play a vital role in the psychological and social functioning, but humans are neither fully aware nor fully unconscious of this role in their social conversations (Jackson, 2005).

3.6.1.2. Social Identity Theory

Evidence suggests that almost every society organizes itself into distinct groups which favour the “in-group” (those within the given reference group) and discriminate against the “out-group” (those outside the group). The “minimal group hypothesis” proposes that the very act of forming social groups leads to in-group identification and competitive inter-group behaviour, even in the absence of goal or scarcity conflicts (Jackson, 2005).

The “Social Identity” theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Hogg & Abrams, 1988; Tajfel, 1978; Turner & Giles, 1981) states that social identification within a “reference group” is a key component of identity.

Social identity seems based on a cognitive awareness of an individual's membership of a group; a positive or negative evaluation of this group membership; and an affective involvement with a particular reference group.

There is a universal human desire for positive social identity. Humans have an in-built tendency to form discrete social groups; to favour in-group members and to discriminate against members of the out-group. This discrimination provides a positive social identity.

Societies have different social structures, but also different belief systems about social mobility.

3.6.2. Pro-social behaviour

Consumer pro-sociality may influence investments in energy efficiency technologies. (Knittel et al, 2014).

3.6.2.1. Private provisions of public goods

The assumption in neoclassical economics is that individuals have an innate tendency to "free ride" (even if others contribute to the public good), as they only care about their own consumption of the public goods and are not affected by the consumption of other individuals. This implies that public goods are underprovided (Pollit et al, 2011).

Behavioural economics may partly explain why and when individuals make private provisions of public goods. The theory provides two alternatives (Pollit et al, 2011):

- The „altruistic incentive“;
- The „warm glow effect“.

3.6.2.1.1. The altruistic incentive

Individuals value their contribution to the provision of social goods. Individuals are "other-regarding", i.e. they also value the consumption of others. A public good may still be underprovided, but only because individuals are "conditional co-operators". They will contribute to the public good, but only if they are certain that others will do the same. In other words, they will contribute if others do not free ride and thus show a concern for fairness (Ostrom, 1998). Moskowitz (1992; 1993a, 1993b) argues that customers would voluntarily sign up and pay higher electricity rates if the additional money collected were earmarked to support renewable energy projects and environmental activities.

3.6.2.1.2. The warm glow effect

The "warm glow effect" refers to the idea that individuals might participate in public goods (like energy efficiency) because it makes them feel good (Andreoni, 1990). This may be the case either because they feel better about themselves, or because they care about what others think of them (Andreoni, 1990; Bernheim and Rangel, 2007).

The contribution of an individual to a public good as a social status symbol, either (because of a desire for a "warm glow effect" or for "prestige", does not necessarily mean that the individual cares about the public benefit per se (Pollit et al, 2011). Consumers may be willing to pay the extra cost of the energy efficient product above and beyond the savings in energy as a sign of **social status** (Knittel et al, 2014).

A monetary incentive may crowd out the motivation to contribute, as it would take away the "warm-glow" satisfaction of giving.

3.6.2.2. Empirical evidence

Laboratory experiments and a small field experiment show that a provision point mechanism (PPM) where individuals make voluntary contributions to a project, with the disclaimer that if the necessary benchmark amount is not collected, the contributions will be refunded, achieve higher contributions than "voluntary contribution mechanisms" (VCM) (Rondeau et al, 1995).

A laboratory experiment revealed that a PPM increased the rate of participation in a renewable energy program significantly above that of a treatment group. A field experiment observed that the PPM sign-up rates were much higher than those from other "voluntary contribution" programs (Rose et al, 2002).

Although monetary incentives may crowd out the motivation to contribute to a public good, "... few studies have demonstrated this effect empirically in the context of energy" (Pollit et al, 2011, p.17). Jacobson et al. (2010) find that, based on billing data of participants and non-participant in a green electricity program in Memphis (U.S.), households participating at the minimum threshold level increase their electricity consumption by 2.5%. The payment for green electricity "crowds out" their motivation to reduce electricity consumption.

Ameli and Brandt (2015) give two examples of how social participation may correlate with residential energy consumption.

- Individuals who show social participation (for instance as member of an NGO) are more likely to be engaged in environmentally responsible behaviour (Olli et al, 2001).
- Membership of an NGO correlates positively with the adoption of energy efficient appliances, light bulbs, heat thermostats and energy efficient windows. Membership of an environmental NGO correlates positively with investments in solar panels and heat pumps (Ameli & Brandt, 2014).

3.6.3. Social norms

Pollit et al (2011) describe the potential influence of social norms on the energy consumption of households. "*Social norms affect individual actions through providing guidelines as to what is acceptable or "normal" behaviour. Some behavioural interventions aim to influence consumer energy consumption through increasing awareness of social norms*" (Pollit et al, 2011, p. 11-12)..

3.6.3.1. Focus Theory of Normative Conduct

The Focus Theory of Normative conducts argues that there exist two kinds of formally and functionally distinct social norms:

- Descriptive norms. A descriptive norm ("what most people do") refers to the perception that an individuals holds of what those in his social group would normally do in a particular situation. Descriptive norms play an adaptive role in behaviour. They provide behavioural examples that help select the appropriate behaviour in a given situation while freeing up cognitive resources for more important tasks. Simon (1976) calls this "procedural" rationality. Descriptive norms carry little moral weight;
- Injunctive norms. An injunctive norm refers to the perception that an individual holds as to what most people would approve or disapprove of. Injunctive norms reflect the moral lines and guidelines of the social group. They motivate and constrain the actions of individuals by promising social rewards and sanctions for acting or not acting in certain ways.

The two kinds of norms may readily apply to the same situation. The Focus Theory of Normative Conduct argues that how an individual responds to a descriptive or injunctive norm depends on which kind of norm is salient (or "in focus") to him in that particular situation. For example:

- If there are no cameras, an individual may follow the descriptive norm of driving "too fast" but at the same speed as everyone else;
- If the individual becomes aware that there are cameras or that there is a patrol car ahead, he will slow down to the speed limit and follow the disjunctive norm (speeding restriction).

Whether an individual installs an efficient heating system or signs up for a green electricity tariff, etc. may be deeply influenced by the existence and salience of descriptive and injunctive social norm (Jackson, 2005).

3.6.3.2. Empirical evidence

Schultz et al. (2007) describe an experiment with 286 households in San Marcos, California, U.S, where the households were provided with energy conservation messages that compared the given household's energy consumption to that of their neighbours. Households with lower than average energy consumption increased their energy consumption (the "Boomerang effect"). The boomerang ef-

fect was eliminated after drawing a smiley next to the energy consumption, which presumably was interpreted as a normative signal.

Nolan et al (2008) describe an experiment similar to that of Schultz et al (2007) with 271 households in San Marcos, California, US. Energy conservation messages that compared a given household's energy consumption to that of their neighbour led to 10% more energy demand reduction than the messages that gave only energy conservation tips.

Allcott & Mullainathan (2010) discuss the results of OPOWER, a large randomized field experiment with 5000,000 households in the U.S. OPOWER mailed home energy report letters to customers, comparing their energy usage to that of their neighbours. The letters also contained energy conservation tips. The intervention reduced average energy demand by 1.11% to 2.78% from the baseline. Costa and Kahn (2010) found that the OPOWER effects were heterogeneous; The electricity conservation "nudge" works with political liberals; and backfires with political conservatives. Loewenstein and Ubel (2010) warned that the energy savings generated by the OPOWER intervention were very small; and that a conventional policy instrument such as a carbon tax would be far more effective.

4. MODELLING FAILURES

4.1. INTRODUCTION TO MODELLING FAILURES

The basic approach of engineering studies is “... to calculate the net present value of a set of possible energy efficiency investments given assumed capital costs, energy prices, investment horizons, and discount rates” (Allcott & Greenstone, 2012, p. 12-13). These studies conclude that large fractions of energy can be saved at “negative” cost. “These engineering studies are a large part of the basis for the claims about the Energy Efficiency Gap” (Allcott & Greenstone, 2012, p. 12).

“Modelling failures” explanations of the energy paradox consist essentially of explaining why observed behaviour is indeed optimal from the point of view of energy users (Jaffe and Stavins, 1994, p. 805).

On a side note, before the advent of “behavioural failures”, modelling failures often were (and still are) called “non-market failures”, to distinguish them from the “market failures” discussed in Chapter 2.

Engineering studies may overestimate future energy savings. “...many analysts believe that estimates of technically feasible savings substantially overstate the energy-efficiency gap” (Austin, 2012, p. 5). Evaluations of the energy efficiency gap often rely on ex ante engineering estimates of energy savings for certain technologies. If these estimates do not accurately reflect true energy savings, they may result in a biased estimate of the energy efficiency gap (Jacobsen & Kotchen, 2012). “To the extent that engineering estimates overestimate energy savings, studies based on such estimates also overestimate the extent of underinvestment in energy efficiency” (Ameli & Brandt, 2015, p. 7).

There are a number of reasons why engineering “bottom up” type studies may understate the costs of energy efficiency investments or overstate the energy savings (Joskow, 1994; Allcott & Greenstone, 2012; Knittel et al, 2014).

The modelling failures discussed in this chapter are:

- Unobserved or understated costs (hidden costs)
- Ignored product attributes
- Heterogeneity of consumers
- Discount rates: Risk – Option Value
- Engineering models and audit tools

4.2. UNOBSERVED OR UNDERSTATED COSTS - HIDDEN COSTS

4.2.1. Theory

Engineering costs typically incorporate only upfront capital costs and omit opportunity costs or other unobserved factors (Allcott & Greenstone, 2012, p. 13). If the engineering calculations of the energy savings potential from apparently cost-effective investments fail to include certain costs, the engineering estimates will overstate the net benefits from energy-efficiency investments (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014, p. 20). Ameli and Brandt (2012) also indicate that studies may fail to fully account for all adoption costs.

A negative cost energy-efficiency investment may turn into a positive cost energy-efficiency investment, when the so-called “hidden costs” are taken into account (Knittel et al, 2014).

Unobserved or understated costs can take many forms. The literature makes a distinction between transaction costs and other unobserved or understated costs, the so-called other hidden costs. Although transaction costs could be considered a “market failure” (in particular **imperfect information**), understating them would be a modelling failure.

4.2.1.1. Transaction costs

New equipment requires time and money for acquiring information about the profitability of the energy efficiency investment or for installing the energy efficiency technology (Ameli & Brandt, 2015). The new product would also have to be as reliable as the more familiar alternative product. It is difficult to learn about the performance and costs of energy efficiency technologies and practices compared to more conventional equipment (Golove & Eto, 1996). These costs are part of the transaction costs. There may also be unobserved implementation costs or cost for the reallocation of resources within a firm (Gerarden et al, 2015). Firms may incur training expenses for operation and maintenance staff when they adopt new technologies (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

Anderson and Newell (2004) give an example of opportunity costs within industry: the time that staff has to spend analysing or implementing new production processes or maintaining new equipment and various project risks, including potential objections of personnel against new equipment or suspected maintenance problem.

4.2.1.2. Other hidden costs

Howarth & Sanstad (1995) argue that other hidden costs, or 'indivisible private costs'—such as the 'hassle' of having energy-efficient equipment installed—are important and should be distinguished from transaction costs that are measurable and easier to price. Hidden costs might be thought of as direct reductions in utility, rather than costs that have an impact on consumers' finances (and therefore also indirectly on their utility). The rationale for separating these costs from transaction costs might be challenged, but separate budget constraints may apply to financial and time resources (Defra, 2006).

Alcott and Greenstone (2012) give as an example the potentially substantial unobserved costs from weatherization, such as: it takes time; it is for most people not highly enjoyable; it requires one or sometimes two home energy audits; and a contractor has to carry out the work, requiring appointments, follow-up visits and paperwork.

4.2.2. Empirical evidence

Transaction costs may range from 3% to 8% of total investment costs in large energy-intensive firms (Hein & Blok, 1994).

Koomey & Sanstad (1994) found that for energy-efficient commercial lighting and refrigerators hidden costs and heterogeneity did not play a relevant role.

The analysis of free energy audits provided by the US-DOE for free to SMEs reveals that nearly half of the investments that engineering assessments showed would have short payback periods were not adopted due to unaccounted costs, such as "lack of staff for analysis/implementation", "risk of inconvenience to personnel" or "suspected risk of problem with equipment" (Anderson & Newell, 2004).

Caird, Roy and Herring (2007, p. 156) find that the hassle of cleaning the attic space prevents installing or upgrading attic insulation.

Sharma, (2011, p. 61) shows that the opportunity costs for adopting thermal insulation are more than twice the costs of materials and labour.

4.3. IGNORED PRODUCT ATTRIBUTES

Ignored product attributes are basically another example of unobserved or understated "opportunity costs", more in particular "other **hidden costs**". Ignored product attributes refer to the decrease in the quality of the energy service provided, For example, more energy-efficient lighting may come at the cost of less pleasing or lower quality light; or a higher vehicle fuel economy may be bundled with less desirable attributes such as small size or less acceleration (Gillingham & Palmer, 2014). Given their relative importance, we prefer to discuss them separately.

4.3.1. Theory

Realistically achievable energy savings depend on consumers' legitimate preferences for product attributes other than energy efficiency (Austin, 2012).

Producers of energy efficiency technologies may introduce energy efficiency improvements by trading off other product attributes. Consumers thus face opportunity costs of decreased product quality, in addition to any price change (Gerarden et al, 2015). These so-called “intangible costs” or “non-financial costs” are very real to households’ contemplation on the adoption of an energy efficiency technology (Jaccard et al, 2010).

The problem in engineering and econometric analysis is “omitted variable bias”. There can be attributes observed by both the analyst and the consumer; attributes observed by the consumer but not by the analyst; attributes observed by the analyst but not by the consumer; and attributes observed by neither (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 34).

The classic example of ignored product attributes is the compact fluorescent lamp (CFL).

A technologist would consider an incandescent light bulb and a compact fluorescent light (CFL) bulb to be perfect substitutes if they both produce 700 lumens of light. This allows the engineer to focus on their different capital costs, electricity use and life expectancies when estimating the profitability of acquiring the more efficient bulb (Jaccard et al, 2010, p. 47). For example, a McKinsey study treated CFLs as interchangeable with other forms of lighting (Granade et al, 2009, p. 52).

Energy efficiency technologies may not be the perfect substitutes suggested by a simple analysis of their services, such as of the amount of lumens produced by efficient and inefficient light bulbs. For much of the first two decades of their commercial availability, compact fluorescent light (CFL) bulbs provided a markedly different quality of service than incandescent bulbs in terms of quality of the light (cold, flickering and ashen), size and appearance of the bulb, timing to reach full intensity (they did not turn on instantly), compatibility with light dimmers, resistance to cold, and other attributes (Jaccard et al, 2010, p. 47). But as quality has improved and prices have come down, the unit sales of compact fluorescent lamps have increased substantially (Austin, 2012, p. 6).

4.3.2. Empirical evidence

There is some evidence that the qualitative attributes of more energy-efficient technologies may be inferior to those of less efficient technologies (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

Berry et al. (1995) and Busse et al. (2013) found that differences in fuel costs between cars are often related to differences in other attributes, such as size, weight and power. In some cases, more fuel efficient vehicles might have less desirable attributes, such as less comfort, slow acceleration and reduced maximum speed.

In theory econometric methods can include product attributes in the analysis. In practice, they are limited by the impracticality of observing and accurately measuring all product characteristics, which are typically subsumed into error terms (Gerarden et al, 2015).

A random-coefficient model incorporating micro-data not only found **heterogeneity** in demand for automobile fuel economy, but also a systematic negative willingness to pay (WTP) for fuel economy. The model controlled for confounding product attributes (for instance weight or horsepower) that are negatively correlated with fuel economy (Pettrin, 2002).

Studies using differencing or fixed effects models and panel data find that consumers correctly value fuel economy (Busse, Knittel & Zettelmeyer, 2013; Sallee, West & Fan, 2009).

A study using differencing or fixed effects models and panel data finds that consumers “undervalue” fuel economy relative to the purchase price of automobiles when choosing between vehicles with different energy efficiency (Allcott and Wozny, 2014).

A study of appliance purchases using transactions data and geographic variation in electricity prices finds that consumers undervalue operating costs on average (Houde, 2014).

4.4. HETEROGENEITY OF CONSUMERS

4.4.1. Theory

An energy efficiency technology or measure may be cost-effective in general, but not in all cases (Jaffe & Stavins, 1994). Some energy efficient technologies may appear profitable on average, they might not be attractive for some part of the population (Jaffe et al., 2004). In effect, consumers are heterogeneous in the degree of their investment inefficiencies (Alcott & Greenstone, 2012, p. 4). A class of consumers consists of a distribution of users. An energy efficiency technology may thus be cost effective on average for the whole class, but for some users in that class the new level of energy efficiency will not be cost-effective (Cagno et al, 2013, p. 292). This implies that energy efficiency policies have to be targeted, by considering what types of consumers are induced to become more energy efficient (Alcott et al, 2012).

The reasons why products that appear financially attractive for the average consumer may not be attractive for certain consumers, are (Alcott & Greenstone, 2012; Golove & Eto 1996):

- Differences in preferences. For example, consumers with higher preferences for future fuel saving choose more fuel efficient products (“**selection bias**”);
- Differences in the expected use of the product. For instance, for a summer home that is only used a few weeks each year, the consumer is better off purchasing a less expensive, less energy efficient air conditioner.

Stavins (2013) states that consumer heterogeneity can be:

- static or „cross-sectional“. This heterogeneity may refer to differences within a country or region, as well as between countries. For example, an energy efficiency technology or measure may be cost-effective in most locations but not in others, leading to an excessive energy saving potential being claimed for the technology for the whole country or region;
- dynamic or „intertemporal“. This heterogeneity refers amongst others to “early adopters” and the presence of an option value to waiting.

An example of the heterogeneity of consumer demand are the effects of weatherization on energy use. Depending on the intensity of use of the dwelling, the benefits of insulation may not be the same for all households.

4.4.2. Empirical evidence

The results regarding the heterogeneity of consumer demand are often mixed (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

Berry, Levinsohn and Pakes (1995), using a random-coefficient model, found heterogeneity in demand for automobile fuel economy, suggesting a small negative willingness to pay (WTP) for fuel economy improvement. This finding may reflect heterogeneity in the distribution of consumer preferences.

Electric space heating that may be uneconomic for a typical home that is occupied throughout the entire year, may constitute a low-cost energy alternative for a summer residence, where the upfront cost of more energy-efficient systems cannot be recovered because of low utilisation rates (Howarth & Sanstad, 1995).

Metcalf and Hassett (1999) estimate the distribution of returns to attic insulation in the U.S. The estimated median and mean returns on investment are on the order of 10 %. But one quarter of the households had returns greater than 13.5 %. The differences in rates of return largely depend on the intensity of use. This heterogeneity implies that although estimates of average returns for adopters may in principle be meaningful in evaluating the costs and benefits of an existing weatherization program; the net returns for adopters overstate the returns for non-adopters.

Bento, Li and Roth (2012) using a Monte Carlo analysis find that consumers differ in their marginal-willingness-to-pay (WTP) for a future reduction in fuel costs. Consumers with higher preferences for future fuel saving choose more fuel efficient products.

4.5. DISCOUNT RATE: RISK – OPTION VALUE

There are basically two ways to identify underinvestment in energy efficiency (Sanstad et al, 2006; Hausman, 1979):

- Compute the net present value (NPV) of energy efficiency measures as the difference of the forecasted energy savings, discounted with the market interest rate, and the upfront investment cost. If many projects with a positive NPV are not taken up, that would reflect underinvestment. In other words, the implicit discount rate that would be higher than the market rate. Studies provide evidence that consumers use high implicit discount rates when making energy efficiency related decisions, sometimes much higher than the markets rates on saving and borrowing (Train, 1985; Hassett & Metcalf, 1993; Sanstad et al, 2006);
- Estimate the consumers' valuation of initial investment costs on the one hand and of the present value of future energy savings on the other hand. If consumers attach a much larger weight to initial investment costs than to future energy savings, there will be underinvestment. For instance, studies suggest that consumers undervalue future gasoline costs relative to car purchase prices when choosing between automobiles with different energy efficiency (Allcott & Wozny, 2012; Busse et al, 2013)

The computation of the NPV can be based on engineering estimates of savings or on estimates that come from actual energy use by households after they invested in energy efficiency (Ameli & Brandt, 2015).

4.5.1. Risk

The energy savings of an energy-efficiency investment occur over the lifetime of the energy efficiency technology. The future gains must be discounted, given the time value of money. The relevant discount rate is the opportunity cost of the capital used for that project (Knittel et al, 2014).

The high (implicit) discount rates for energy efficiency investments and the rejection of particular energy-efficiency technologies may represent a rational response to risk (Cagno et al, 2013). Risk is a barrier to energy efficiency, because accurate estimates of the net costs of implementing energy efficiency measures depend on future economic conditions in general, and on future energy prices and availability in particular (Stern & Aronson, 1984). The uncertainty surrounding energy savings, fluctuations in energy prices and the irreversibility of the investment imply that energy efficiency investments are particularly risky. As consumers tend to be risk-averse, such concerns have been found to be very important for decision-makers, strongly affecting consumer decisions (Hirst and Brown, 1990). Given the uncertainty about future returns combined with the irreversibility of the investment, the use of high discount rates for energy-efficiency investments is rational (Sutherland, 2003). Riskier investment require higher returns.

This risk differential between technology substitutes is also a function of newness. More efficient technologies are usually newer technologies and because these tend to fail more frequently their capital cost should be multiplied by a factor different than that applied to a conventional technology Engineering studies do not adjust the capital costs of the energy efficiency technology to reflect this risk (Jacquard et al, 2010).

The high (implicit) discount rates required by consumers for energy efficiency investments either reflect real opportunity costs, in which case the discount rates are appropriate; or are symptomatic of other barriers to investment in energy efficiency, in which case the focus should be on these other barriers, not on discount rates (Defra, 2006).

4.5.2. Option value – the value of waiting

Investments in energy efficiency technologies are often long-term investments (Knittel et al, 2014). There may be a value to delaying the energy efficiency investment, if

- end-users expect the cost of the energy-efficiency technology to fall over time, for instance because of learning-by-doing (LBD) effects or technological progress. Potential technological innovation which would reduce future adoption costs may thus yield a value for delaying energy-efficiency investments (Jaffe & Stavins, 1995; Ansar and Sparks, 2009). Investors may benefit from waiting for the arrival of even better technologies, rather than adopt new technologies immediately, even if those new technologies appear to be profitable (Van Soest & Bulte, 2001; Anderson & Newell, 2004);
- energy prices are uncertain.

The “option value” is the net benefit of delaying an investment even when the investment’s net present value (NPV) is positive. Metcalf (1994) argues that option values in particular explain why the rates of return required by consumers from energy efficiency investments might exceed market interest rates. van Soest & Bulte (2001) also state that since investments in energy efficiency technologies are partly irreversible, it may be beneficial to postpone investment until newer and better technologies become available.

The option value theory assumes:

- irreversibility
- uncertainty
- flexible timing
- lumpiness of investment.

Each of these assumptions may fail (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 32-33). Energy-efficiency investments can be reversible, for example due to the presence of resale markets. Uncertainty may be relatively unimportant, for instance for products such as light bulbs with relatively short lifetimes. Timing of investments is not always flexible, such as for the replacement of a domestic hot water (DHW) heater.

The option value of waiting may play *some part* in explaining the energy efficiency gap.

4.5.3. Empirical evidence

It remains unclear whether risk, uncertainty and irreversibility of some energy efficiency investments can explain the apparent underinvestment in energy-efficient technologies (Ameli & Brandt, 2015, p. 10).

The capital asset pricing model (CAPM) provides a static optimization framework for determining the appropriate hurdle rate for an (energy efficiency) investment. A negative correlation between energy prices and the rest of the economy would support the use of low hurdle (discount) rates for energy efficiency investments, because those energy efficiency Investments can serve as a hedge (Gerarden et al, 2015, p. 32-33). A study by Metcalf (1994) does find a negative correlation between consumer price index (CPI) for fuels and the S&P 500 index. Allcott and Wozny (2014) find a low correlation between annual changes in gasoline prices and market returns. That would lower the discount rate in an analysis of vehicle purchases. However, the CAPM may fail as a benchmark for discount rates for energy-efficiency investments because 1) CAPM assumes that investment opportunities, expected returns and risk relationships are static instead of dynamic; 2) CAPM assumes zero transaction costs, resale markets and diversified portfolios; and 3) CAPM has failed numerous empirical tests (Fama & French, 2004).

An analysis by Hassett and Metcalf (1993) of irreversible investment in energy efficiency measures under conditions of energy-price uncertainty explains the observed technology adoption rates without the need to invoke “market failures”.

A number of studies challenge the conclusion that the option value of waiting can explain the high implicit discount rates.

- [Howarth & Sanstad \(1995\)](#) find that the high implicit discount rates mask other effects, but they consider that asymmetric information, bounded rationality and transaction costs are more important than the option value of waiting; .
- For higher discount rates (for example 30%) the hurdle rates for irreversible investments under uncertainty are similar to the discount rates predicted by the conventional (neoclassical) model ([Sanstad et al, 1995](#));
- [Baker \(2012\)](#) points out that the use of “option values” to explain the energy efficiency gap may be true for yes/no decisions (for example adding insulation to a home or not); but may not be true for decisions regarding multiple technologies (for example buying a SUV instead of a compact car).

4.6. ERRONEOUS ENGINEERING MODELS

So far we discussed some of the reasons why households may not take up seemingly profitable energy efficiency investments. But the calculations of the engineering models may simply be wrong, implying that the energy efficiency measures that are implemented do not deliver the promised energy (cost) savings.

For example, building energy models simulate the energy required for heating, cooling, lighting and equipment loads of a building. These models are also used to estimate the energy efficiency potential in the building stock. The accuracy of these models is critical to delivering cost effective energy efficiency improvements ([Fowlie, 2013](#)).

There are relatively few comparisons of ex ante estimated and ex post observed energy efficiency savings.

[Nadel and Keating \(1991\)](#) relate overestimating future energy savings to erroneous assumptions in the engineering estimates, particularly over-estimating lighting system operating hours; ignoring complex interactions, such as rooms that are unheated or only partially heated; and quality control problems during measure installation, commissioning and maintenance.

A research team from the University of Chicago and the University of California, Berkeley, conducted a field test of one energy efficiency program: the Federal Weatherization Assistance Program (WAP) ([Fowlie et al, 2015](#)). Federal regulations require that for a measure (e.g. insulation improvements, air sealing, heating system upgrades) to be implemented under WAP, it must pass a cost-benefit analysis (projected cumulative energy savings must be greater than the investment costs). The cost-benefit analysis is based on an in-home energy audit conducted using an engineering model, the National Energy Audit Tool (NEAT). The analysis by [Fowlie et al \(2015\)](#) was based on a randomized controlled trial (RCT) conducted with a sample of more than 30,000 WAP-eligible households in the state of Michigan. Some of the main findings are:

- The costs of the energy efficiency investments are about double households' energy savings;
- The energy savings projected in advance by engineering calculations are roughly 2.5 times the savings found by the study, underscoring that these models' results must be validated in the field;
- There is no evidence that the shortfall in energy savings is a result of the „rebound effect“.

It is important to note that the study did not include hidden costs, such as the “*hassle and effort that households expend to implement a weatherization retrofit, even one with zero out of pocket costs*” (epic.uchicago.edu/news-events/news/do-residential-energy-efficiency-investments-deliver July 7, 2015).

The studied energy efficiency investments save far less energy than expected, hence their return on investment (ROI) is lower than projected. The gap between modelled and observed energy efficiency is attributed to a systematic overestimation of the efficiency gains by engineering models and audit tools.

The study concludes with the following policy recommendations (Fowlie et al, 2015):

- Policy-makers should use market-based approaches rather than policies justified by projected energy savings, because actual energy savings fall far short of these projections;
 - Policy-makers should ensure that energy efficiency investments deliver the promised energy savings by relying on field studies that use state-of-the-art evaluation techniques (like randomized trials);
- The engineering models should be adjusted to match the field evidence, in order to deliver the true impacts and not the potential ones.

5. PREFERENCE ELICITATION WITH MCDA

5.1. INTRODUCTION

We know that behavioural economics have thus far avoided the fundamental question of how to reconcile revealed preference theory with the existence of behavioural failures. This chapter gives a broad overview of MCDA techniques, to discover whether preference elicitation with MCDA may provide part of the answer.

The objective of multicriteria decision aiding (MCDA) is the ex-ante assessment of a few individual alternatives by explicitly considering the subjective preferences of a decision maker for the purpose of decision support (Geldermann & Treitz, 2008). Munda (2003, p. 4) states that the main purpose of MCDA is to elicit "... clear subjective preferences from a mythical decision maker and then a well-structured mathematical decision problem thanks to a more or less sophisticated algorithm."

One can reduce the number alternatives to be evaluated by only looking at Pareto efficient solutions.

Most multi-objective techniques use the concept of domination. When two solutions in the feasible solution space are compared, it is said that solution p dominates q if the solution p is no worse than q in all objectives and solution p is strictly better than q in at least one objective (de Souza, 2011). In other words, a non-dominated solution is one for which no criteria can be improved without a simultaneous detriment to at least one of the others. All non-dominated alternatives are called efficient in a decision problem (Geldermann & Treitz, 2008). It follows that a solution is dominated if there is another solution which excels it in one or more criteria and equals it in the remainder. Dominated solutions are called inefficient.

Figure 6 Pareto frontier in two dimensions

A set of solutions in a MCDA problem is Pareto efficient (also called non-dominated), if their elements are feasible solutions such that no other feasible solution can achieve the same or better performance for all the criteria being strictly better for at least one criterion. Stated differently, for a Pareto efficient solution one cannot improve the value of at least one of its criteria without worsening the value of at least one other criterion. The Pareto frontier is thus composed of non-dominated solutions (Xiaoqian, 2012). This is a necessary condition to guarantee the rationality of any solution to an MCDA problem (De Montis et al, 2000). Solutions that do not belong to this set are referred to as non Pareto efficient (also called dominated). Dominated solutions do not represent rational choices, as one can always find another solution that is objectively better.

A two-dimensional Pareto frontier for the minimization of two criteria is illustrated in figure 1.

In principle, a decision-maker always has to choose a solution from the Pareto frontier. A decision-maker may sometimes choose an alternative that is not on the Pareto frontier because a criterion is hard to quantify or is not present in the data set. MCDA tries to capture all decision criteria, no matter what the nature of the data is (Borer, 2005, p. 15).

For non-trivial problems there are many Pareto efficient solutions. MCDA methods seek to reduce incomparability by explicitly incorporating preferential information of the decision-maker. The selection of one final solution out of the mathematically equivalent set of Pareto optimal solutions is not a purely mathematical question which can be addressed objectively (Geldermann & Treitz, 2008). There exists a wide range of literature about elicitation of value judgements, preference modelling, and the ability of the decision-maker to provide this information.

MCDA is a tool for comparative evaluation only. Solving an MCDA problem is not searching for an optimal solution. The concept of an optimum does not exist in a MCDA framework. MCDA can therefore not be justified within the optimization paradigm adopted in traditional Operations Research (OR) (Belton & Stewart, 2002, p. 3). In the absence of an optimum solution, a commitment solution may be acceptable and/or judged as satisfactory (Ferreira et al, 2011).

The active involvement of decision-makers makes MCDA both time and resource intensive. However, decisions are seldom objective; and MCDA is a tool that makes subjective judgments transparent (Barfod & Leleur, 2014, p. 23).

5.2. CHARACTERISTICS OF MCDA PROBLEMS

Multicriteria decision aiding (MCDA) is both an approach and a set of techniques.

The main goal of multicriteria decision aiding (MCDA) is to help the decision maker(s) to make decisions (Yevseyave, 2012).

The problem of the decision-maker consists of evaluating a finite set of alternatives in order to find the best one (i.e. to identify the single most preferred alternative); to rank them from the best to the worst (i.e. to select a limited number of alternatives), to group them into predefined homogeneous classes, or to describe how well each alternative meets all the criteria simultaneously (Zavadskas & Turskis, 2011) (Fülop, 2005).

5.2.1.1. MCDA problem types

The most common problem types in MCDA are choice, ranking, and sorting (de Souza, 2011):

- Choice. The purpose is to select a small number (as small as possible) of fitted alternatives in a way that a single alternative may be chosen in the end. This does not mean that selection is necessarily focused only on finding a single solution. It can be oriented to find a subset of optimal solutions, from the original set, where such subset contains all the most satisfying alternatives, which remain non-comparable between each other;
- Ranking. The purpose is to find a complete or partial preorder of a set of alternatives. This preorder is a result from a comparison between all the alternatives in the set. The preorder allows to “judge” the alternatives in order to find a rank. The rank can be attributed to each alternative or to a subset of alternatives where each one inside is indifferent to each other;
- Sorting. The purpose is to assign each alternative from a set of alternatives to a category in a set of pre-defined categories. In such cases, the alternatives are evaluated in order to fulfil the (minimum) requirements to belong to a category. For instance, in a car selection MCDA problem, the categories might be „cars I like and ready to buy“; „cars I like but not ready to buy“; and „cars I don't like and not ready to buy“.

5.2.1.2. Characteristics of MCDA problems

MCDA problems share a number of characteristics:

- Multiple criteria. The criteria can be objectives or attributes. The fundamental idea of the MCDA approach is to model a problem considering different criteria, rather than a single criterion as in conventional optimization techniques (Ferreira et al, 2011). MCDA approaches are generally used for decision problems with various objectives (Omann, 2000). The options or

alternatives may differ in the extent to which they achieve several objectives (Communities UK, 2009);

- Conflicting among criteria. The multiple criteria may conflict with each other. Some conflict or trade-off is mostly evident among the objectives. No one option or alternative will be obviously best in achieving all objectives. For instance, more beneficial options or alternatives may be more costly and/or riskier (Communities UK, 2009);
- Incommensurable units. The criteria may have different units of measurement. There is a variety of scales to measure the criteria. The criteria could be real numbers; logical (extended) values (for example: true, false, possible, less possible, etc.); ranks (for example, subjective marks assigned by human deciders) or linguistics appreciations or qualifying properties (such as good, bad, remarkable, etc.) or other ranking information (Vaduva, 2012). Some criteria can be transformed into quantitative indicators, other criteria use qualitative parameters. Qualitative parameters can be used directly as linguistic variables, or can be transformed into cardinal ones and then used as quantitative variables (Omann, 2000).

As a set of techniques, MCDA provides different ways of disaggregating a complex problem, of measuring the extent to which alternatives achieve objectives, and of weighting the objectives (Communities UK, 2009).

5.2.2. Objectives, attributes and criteria

5.2.2.1. The relationship between criteria, attributes and objectives

The distinctions among criteria, attributes, and objectives are made as follows (Xiaoqian, 2012, p. 39) (Goodwin, 2003):

- Criterion. A criterion is a measure of performance when evaluating an alternative. A criterion emerges as a form of attribute or objective;
- Attribute. An attribute is an inherent characteristic of an alternative. An attribute is used to measure performance in relation to an objective. A proxy attribute is an attribute not directly related to the objective;
- Objective. An objective is an indication of preferred direction of movement, i.e. 'minimize' or 'maximize' (Goodwin, 2003). It indicates the direction of change desired. An attribute with a direction us an objective.

Figure 7 The relationship among criteria, attributes and objectives

For example, level of comfort is a criterion when evaluating an aircraft, cabin volume and noise are attributes of the aircraft which can be used to measure the level of comfort, the maximization of cabin volume and the minimization of noise are objectives in the aircraft design process (Xiaoqian, 2012, p. 39).

5.2.2.2. Types of criteria

In relation to the required direction, there are two types of evaluation criteria:

- Benefit (type) criteria. The higher performance level (rating) is better. That is, the higher the criterion value, the more its preference. Benefit criteria offer increasing monotonic utility;

- Cost (type) criteria. The lower performance level (rating) is better. That is, the lower the criterion on value, the more its preference. Cost criteria offer decreasing monotonic utility.

Benefit and cost criteria are also called beneficial and non-beneficial criteria (attributes).

Evaluation criteria can be classified as objective or subjective. The performance ratings of objective criteria are expressed using quantitative values. The performance ratings of subjective criteria are expressed using qualitative (often linguistic) variables.

Possible criteria scales are (Yevseyeva, 2012):

- Ratio/Quantitative/Cardinal. There is information on the difference between scale values with respect to a non-arbitrary origin (for example, meters, kg, etc.);
- Interval. There is information on the difference between scale values with respect to an arbitrary origin (for example Fahrenheit and Celsius temperature scales).
- Ordinal/Qualitative/Verbal. There is order on the scale but no information on the difference between scale values (for example, excellent, good, satisfactory, bad).

5.2.2.3. Principles to select criteria

The following principles are used to select the major criteria used for MCDA (Fülop, 2005; Wang et al, 2009; Sullivan et al, 2012):

- Completeness. The criteria should be complete to include all the objectives of the decision-maker and all the attributes of concern. All essential criteria should be considered. All criteria, collectively, are assumed sufficient for selecting, ranking or ordering the alternatives;
- Conciseness (minimum size). Criteria should be few in number, and should not be decomposed beyond the level where they can be evaluated. Only the smallest number of criteria that can adequately capture the decision problem should be used. The use of a few real discriminators results in a more understandable decision analysis. Too few criteria limits discriminating among alternatives;
- Consistency. The criteria should be consistent with the objectives of the decision-maker;
- Relevance. Each criterion should measure something important;
- Operability – understandability & measurability.
 - Understandability. Criteria should be meaningful. All participants to the decision-making process should have a clear understanding of the meaning of the criteria;
 - Measurability. The criteria should be measurable, if possible quantitatively, if not qualitatively;
- Mutual independence. Each criterion should capture a unique dimension of the decision problem and be independent from other criteria. No overlap or double counting (duplicates) should exist between the different criteria.
- Comparability. The criteria should be able to discriminate among the alternatives and to support the comparison of the performance of the alternative in a meaningful way. For example, if the colour of all alternatives is the same or the user is indifferent to the colour selection, then colour should not be a criterion (US-DOE, 2001). Additionally, the criteria should be normalized when there are both benefit criteria and cost criteria.

Choosing criteria is a subjective process, and usually the result of group consensus (Sullivan et al, 2012).

5.2.3. Decision matrix

An MCDA problem generally involves m alternatives evaluated on n criteria. Let $A_1, \dots, A_i, \dots, A_m$ denote the m alternatives and $C_1, \dots, C_j, \dots, C_n$ the n criteria, respectively.

A standard feature of MCDA is a decision matrix, also known as a “decision table”, a “performance matrix” or a “consequence table”. The $(m \times n)$ decision matrix summarizes the “raw data” available to the decision-maker. In the decision matrix each row belongs to an alternative and each column corre-

sponds to a criterion being considered. Each element x_{ij} of the decision matrix describes the performance (sometimes¹ known as “score” or “rating”) of alternative A_i against criterion C_j . If the performance is expressed in numerical terms, x_{ij} is called the value of criterion C_j with respect to alternative A_i . In other words, x_{ij} is the j^{th} criterion value of the i^{th} alternative.

In a basic form of MCDA the decision matrix may be the final product of the analysis. The decision makers are then left with the task of assessing the extent to which their objectives are met by the entries in the matrix. Such intuitive processing of the data can be speedy and effective, but it may also lead to the use of unjustified assumptions, causing incorrect ranking of alternatives (Communities UK, 2009).

Figure 8 The decision matrix

		critereon	...	critereon	...	critereon
		C_1	...	C_j	...	C_n
Alternative	A_1	x_{11}	...	x_{1j}	...	x_{1n}
	\vdots	\vdots		\vdots		\vdots
Alternative	A_i	x_{i1}	...	x_{ij}	...	x_{in}
	\vdots	\vdots		\vdots		\vdots
Alternative	A_m	x_{m1}	...	x_{mj}	...	x_{mn}

All but the most basic MCDA techniques require additional information from the decision-maker. The majority of MCDA methods require preference information on inter-criteria and intra-criteria comparisons.

Weights $w_1, \dots, w_j, \dots, w_n$ can be assigned to the criteria. In principle, a weight w_j reflects the relative importance of criteria C_j to the decision, and is assumed to be positive. For compensatory methods such as the linear aggregation methods [e.g. simple additive weighting (SAW)] the criteria weights are not so much “importance” coefficients as “trade off” coefficients. The aggregation of several criteria implies taking a position on “compensability”. Compensability refers to the existence of trade-offs, i.e. the possibility of offsetting a disadvantage on some criteria by an advantage on another criterion. The weights can be implicitly or explicitly determined. The weights of the criteria are usually determined on subjective basis. They represent the opinion of a single decision maker or synthesize the opinions of a group of experts using a group decision technique (Fülop, 2005).

5.3. STEPS IN THE MCDA PROCESS

The main steps of the MCDA process are the following (Zavadskas & Turskis, 2011) (Communities UK, 2009):

1. Establish the decision-making context. What are the main goals of the decision-making problem?. Who are the key actors?
2. Identify the main criteria by which the alternatives are to be judged;
3. Generate a finite number of feasible alternatives that can be implemented to achieve the goals of the problem;
4. Describe the expected performance of each alternative against the criteria. If the MCDA is to include steps 5 and 6, also „score“ the alternatives. **Scoring** implies assessing the value associated with the consequences of each option;
5. Weighting. Evaluate the impact of each criterion on the decision making. A decision-maker should express preferences in terms of the relative importance of criteria. One approach is to introduce criteria weights;
6. Combine the scores and weights for each of the alternatives to derive an overall value. Mathematical routines, which may be written into computer programmes, combine the two compo-

¹ We prefer to use “scoring” or “rating” to denote the transformation of the raw performance data to standardized values.

nents („scoring“ and „weighting“) to give an overall assessment of each alternative being appraised;

7. Examine the results;
8. Conduct a sensitivity analyse of the results to changes in scores and weights.

This approach therefore requires decision-makers to provide those inputs that they are best suited to provide, and leaves computers the task of handling detailed information in a way that is consistent with the preferences that have been revealed by these human inputs (Communities UK, 2009).

An MCDA method has to solve the following problems (Vaduva, 2012):

- To make the set of criteria homogeneous. The attributes are often of different types (real numbers, ranks, linguistic appreciations).
- To determine the best probability (weight) vector of importance of alternatives.
- To apply adequate mathematical models to provide the final solution to the MCDA problem.

5.3.1. Scoring

The expected consequences of each alternative can be assigned a *numerical* score on a strength of preference scale for each alternative for each criterion.

The first consideration when setting up consistent numerical scales for the assessment of the criteria is to ensure that the sense of direction is the same in all cases. Better levels of performance should lead to higher value scores (Communities UK, 2000).

It is conventional to allot a value score to each criterion between 0 and 100 on an interval scale. The advantage of an interval scale is that differences in scores have consistency within each criterion. It does not allow the conclusion that a score of 60 represent a performance which on any absolute standard is three times as good as a score of 20 (Communities UK, 2000).

The first step in establishing an interval scale for a criterion is to define the levels of performance corresponding to any two reference points on the scale (Communities UK, 2000): :

- Global scaling: A score of 0 represent the worst level of performance that is likely to be encountered in the decision problem of the general type that is being addressed, and a score of 100 represents the best level Global scaling more easily accommodates new alternatives at a later stage. It requires extra judgment in the defining of the extremes of the scale. It also lends itself less easily (relative to local scaling) to the construction of relative weights for the different criteria; .
- Local scaling: A score of 0 is associated with the performance level of the alternative in the currently considered set of alternatives which performs least well; and 100 with that which performs best.

Once the end points are established for each criterion, there are three ways in which scores may be established for the options (Communities UK, 2000):

- Value function. A value function translates a measure of achievement on the criterion concerned into a value score on the 0 – 100 scale. The value function can be linear or non-linear;
- Direct rating. The judgment of an expert is used to simply associate a number in the 0 – 100 range with the value of each alternative on that criterion. Direct rating is used when a commonly agreed scale of measurement for the criterion in question does not exist, or where there is not the time nor the resources to undertake the measurement.
- Verbal pairwise assessments. A series of verbal pairwise assessments expressing a judgement of the performance of each alternative relative to each of the others is elicited from the decision-maker.

5.3.2. Normalization

It is not always possible or even desirable to assign a numerical score.

An alternative in MCDA is usually described by quantitative and qualitative criteria. The criteria have different units of measurement.

A standard step in processing the data prior to aggregation is the normalization step. Normalization aims at obtaining comparable scales of the criteria values. Different techniques of criteria value normalization are used. The impact of the decision-matrix normalization methods on the decision results has been investigated by many authors (Zavadskas & Turskis, 2011).

There are various methods for normalization. All the normalization methods transform the cardinal decision matrix A into a normalized matrix $R = (r_{ij})$, $0 \leq r_{ij} \leq 1$. (Vaduva, 2012). Normalization methods include (Tofallis, 2013) :

- Ratio normalization (with all criteria scales in the $[0,1]$ interval). For each criterion to be maximized, each score is divided by the largest value. This causes the largest value on each criterion to equal unity and all others represent a fraction of the largest value. One can express each value as a percentage of the largest observed score on that criterion. The formula is $r = x/x_{max}$. For a criterion to be minimized to formula is $r = x_{max}/x$.
- Range normalization or „normalization of ratio difference“ (with all criteria scales in the $[0,1]$ interval). The largest value is converted to 1 (see divide by the largest value), and the lowest observed value is converted to 0. The range has an actual observation at each end. All criteria have an equal range. The formula is as follows: the range normalized score $r = \frac{(x - x_{min})}{(x_{max} - x_{min})}$ where x_{min} and x_{max} are the largest and smallest observed values. For those criteria where lower scores are preferred, the numerator is replaced by $(x_{max} - x)$. Range normalization destroys proportionality. If on raw score is double that of another, the proportionality will not be preserved for the range normalized score.
- Dividing by the total. For each criterion the all the values are added together, and each one of them is divided by this total. This allows scores to be viewed as proportions of some whole. The proportionality of the scores is retained.
- Euclidean normalization (non-linear transformation). The formula is $r = \frac{x}{\sqrt{\sum x^2}}$.
- Z-scores (statistical standardization). Standardized scores (z-scores) are obtained by subtracting the mean and then dividing by the standard deviation. Proportionality is lost. Z-scores are sensitive to outliers. One or more extreme observations can make the mean value extremely unrepresentative.

5.3.3. Weighting

Weights are assigned to the criteria to indicate their relative importance. Different weights directly influence the decision-making results. Formal MCDA techniques usually provide an explicit relative weighting system for the different criteria (Communities UK, 2009).

The weighting within an MCDA is context specific since no objective values exist. The normalisation of criterion weights in the MCDA approaches has been identified as a procedural source of biases (Geldermann & Treitz, 2008).

Preference information describes the decision-maker's attitude in favour of one criterion over another when choosing between alternatives, usually in the form of weighting factors (Xiaoqian, 2012).

There are various weighting methods (Wang et al, 2009; Xiaoqian, 2012).

5.3.3.1. The direct assignment method

The direct assignment method directly assigns numbers to represent the relative importance of one criterion over others. For example, a ten-point scale can be chosen and calibrated so that 0 stands for “extremely low” importance of the criterion; 10 for “extremely high”.

Table 4 The direct assignment method

Criterion evaluation	Value
Extremely low	0
Very low	1.0
Low	3.0
Average	5.0
Very high	9.0
Extremely high	10.0

The numerical assignment is arbitrary. The scaling assumes that a scale value of 9 (very high importance) is three times as important as a scale value of 3 (low importance). The scaling also assumes that the difference between 3 (low importance) and 5 (average importance) is the same as the difference between 5 (average importance) and 9 (very high importance). The method is popular because of its simplicity. However, in complex decision making problems even an experienced decision-maker can find it difficult to precisely assign direct weights for all criteria.

5.3.3.2. The equal weights method

The criteria weight in the equal weights method is defined as $w_j = \frac{1}{n}$

The equal weights method requires minimal knowledge of the decision-maker’s priorities and minimal input from the decision maker. The equal weights method is very popular. It is sometimes argued that this method often produces results nearly as good as those optimal weighting methods. It is criticized because it ignores the relative importance among criteria.

5.3.3.3. The rank-order weighting methods

The criteria weights in the rank-order weighting method are defined as $w_1 \geq w_2 \geq \dots \geq w_n \geq 0$, where $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

The rank-order weighting methods are classified into three categories:

- Subjective weighting methods. The criteria weights depend only on the preferences of the decision-makers, not on an analysis of the initial data. Examples of subjective weighting methods are SMART, SWING, pairwise comparison and AHP.
- Objective weighting method. The criteria weights are obtained by mathematical methods based on the analysis of the initial data. Examples of objective weighting methods are the entropy method, TOPSIS, and the vertical and horizontal methods.
- Combination weighting methods. It is possible to combine subjective and objective weighting methods.

We discuss a selection of the rank-order weighting methods.

5.3.3.4. The SMART weighting method

The Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique was originally developed as a whole process of rating alternatives and weighting criteria. The weights are obtained in two steps:

- Step 1. Rank the importance of the changes in the criteria from the worst criterion levels to the best criterion levels;
- Step 2. Make ratio estimates of the relative importance of each criterion relative to the one ranked lowest in importance. The second step usually begins with assigning ten points to the

least important criterion. The relative importance of the other criteria are then evaluated by giving them points from ten upwards.

The weights are calculated by normalizing the sum of the points to one.

The SMARTER method is an improved version of SMART which only uses the ranking of criteria to derive the weights. SMARTER uses the rank order centroid (ROC) method, so that the weight is calculated as $w_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k}$

5.3.3.5. The SWING weighting method

The SWING method is an algebraic, decomposed, direct procedure weighting method.

The decision maker begins by rank ordering criteria in terms of their associated value ranges. First the respondent is asked to select the criterion that he would most prefer to change from its worst to its best level and to assign 100 points to this most important criterion. Then the respondent is asked to choose the criterion for which a change from the worst to the best level would be considered the second most desirable improvement and to assign points less than 100 to that criterion change. Proceeding in this fashion, the decision maker ranks all criteria and assigns relative importance points to their value ranges. Finally the given points are normalized to sum up to one to get the criteria weights.

5.3.3.6. The eigenvector method (pairwise comparison, AHP)

The eigenvector method uses pairwise comparisons between criteria. It is an analytical way of eliciting preference information of criteria that is used in the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP).

The relative weights of criteria can be obtained by solving the eigenvalue function $M * W = \lambda_{max} * W$ where M is the comparison matrix (i.e. the matrix that represents the pairwise comparisons between criteria), λ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue of the comparison matrix M; and the normalized eigenvector $W = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ corresponding to the maximum eigenvalue are the weights of the criteria.

In AHP, the consistency of the weights is assessed by the Consistency Ratio (CR), where $CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$ with CI is the Consistency Index and RI is the Random Consistency Index.

The Consistency Index (CI) is calculated by the equation $CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$

The Random Consistency index (RI) is an average value derived from a large sample of reciprocal matrices having all elements varying from 1/9 to 9. A CR of 0.1 or less is usually considered acceptable.

5.3.3.7. The entropy method

The entropy method assigns a small weight to a criterion when all the alternatives have similar values on the criterion.

The weights of the criteria can be calculated as follows

$$w_j = \frac{d_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n d_j}$$

where

$d_j = 1 - E_j$ is the degree of diversity of the information involved in the j-th criterion value;

$E_j = -\frac{1}{\ln m} \sum_{i=1}^n p_{ij} \ln p_{ij}$ is the entropy of the j-th criterion value; and

$p_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij}}$ is the value of the j-th criterion ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$).

5.3.3.8. The TOPSIS method

The principle of TOPSIS is that the selected best alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution in geometrical sense.

The weighted distance between alternative A_i and the ideal solution A^* is defined as

$$h_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^2 (x_{ij} - x_j^*)^2$$

Next the following optimization model is solved, from which the weights can be elicited.

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^m h_i = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^2 (x_{ij} - x_j^*)^2 \text{ s. t. } \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, w_j \geq 0$$

5.4. OVERVIEW OF MCDA METHODS

A large number of methods have been developed for solving MCDA problems. MCDA methods have appeared in a rather diffuse way, without any clear general methodology or basic theory (Pirdashti et al, 2011). The methods are characterized by the way in which the preferences of the decision-maker(s) are specified; and the Pareto efficient solution that best fits the given preferences is determined.

5.4.1. MODM and MADM

The first categorization makes a distinction between multi-objective decision making (MODM) and multi-attribute decision making (MADM).

MODM methods are designed to solve problems which require a selection from continuous sets of alternatives. The solution or decision space is continuous. An infinite number of solutions (alternatives) are implicitly defined by a set of constraints on a vector of decision variables. The solutions are implicitly bound in a feasible region, and optimised in this region. MODM methods have been widely studied by means of mathematical programming methods with well-formulated theoretical frameworks. MODM methods are also referred to as Multiple Criteria Design problems or Continuous Multiple Criteria problems.

MADM methods are designed for selecting from multi-attribute discrete alternatives. The solution or decision space is discrete. MADM problems are also referred to as Multiple Criteria Evaluation problems, Discrete Multiple Criteria problems, or Selection problems. The amount of alternatives within a MODM approach is not predetermined (De Montis et al, 2000).

There exists a large number of methods to solve MADM problems which depend of the information the decision-maker has about the problem.

5.4.2. Classifications of MCDA / MCDM methods

5.4.2.1. American and European school of MADM methods

There are two schools of MADM methods: Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) developed by the American school, and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis/Aid (MCDA) created by the European school.

- The American school methods (also called “classical approaches”) rely on numerical estimates and aggregation operations. They are based on the assumption that clear judgements exist about utility values of the attributes and their weightings, which can be formalised within the multi-criteria technique (De Montis et al, 2000). These methods include Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) / Multi-Attribute Value Theory (MAVT); Simple multi-attribute rating technique (SMART); Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP); and Generalized Means (Fülop, 2005);
- The European school methods (also called the „outranking approaches”) rely on the use of relations for the modelling and aggregation of preference information. They are based on the assumption that the preferences are not apparent to the decision maker, and therefore the decision support aims at giving insights into the consequences of different weightings. The main difference with the ‘classical’ MCA methods is the consideration of weak preferences and in-

comparable criteria (De Montis et al, 2000). The most prominent examples are ELECTRE and PROMETHEE.

Most researchers use the terms MADM, MCDM and MCDA interchangeably. We use the term MCDA to denote both MCDM and MCDA methods.

5.4.2.2. Compensatory and non-compensatory methods

A single dimension analysis means that all criteria can be converted to a common measurement scale, such as monetary equivalents (e.g. euros) or utility equivalents (e.g. "utiles", a dimensionless unit of worth ranging from 0 to 1 or from 0 to 100). Full-dimension analysis means that no attempt is made to create a common scale.

A single dimension analysis can make a complex problem computationally tractable and allows trade-offs among criteria. Models for single dimension analysis are called compensatory. Full-dimension analysis allow eliminating inferior alternatives from further analysis and do not allow trade-offs among criteria. Models for full-dimension analysis are called non-compensatory.

The following distinction is often made between non-compensatory and compensatory methods:

- The non-compensatory MCDA methods do not permit trade-offs between criteria. These methods are credited for their simplicity. Those methods include amongst others the DOMINANCE method, the MINIMAX method, the MAXIMIN method, the DISJUNCTIVE (constraint) method, the CONJUNCTIVE (constraint) method, the LEXICOGRAPHIC method, LEXICOGRAPHIC SEMI-ORDERING, ELIMINATION BY ASPECT, the PERMUTATION method and ELECTRE;
- The compensatory methods permit a trade-off between criteria. That is, small changes in one criterion can be offset by opposing changes in other criteria. Compensatory methods assume that the decision maker is able to express his preference of a criterion over another criterion by means of how much of a criterion he would sacrifice in order to obtain higher value of the other criterion. The compensatory methods include amongst others SAW (simple additive weighting); multiplicative weighting, MAUT/MAVT; TOPSIS; AHP; and PROMETHEE.

The compensatory methods can be further divided into three subgroups:

- Scoring models. They select an alternative that has the highest score, reducing the decision problem to assessing the appropriate multi-attribute utility/value function. Methods include simple additive weighting, interactive simple additive weighing;
- Compromising models. They identify the alternative which is closes to the ideal solution. Methods include TOPSIS, LINMAP and nonmetric MRS methods;
- Concordance models. They identify a set of preference rankings which best satisfy a given concordance measure. Method include LINEAR ASSIGNMENT and ELECTRE.

5.4.2.3. MCDM methods according to available information

MCDM methods can be grouped according to the available information. Hwang and Yoon (1981) group the MCDM methods as follows:

- Methods that require no preference information from the decision-maker on criteria and alternatives. Methods include the DOMINANCE, MAXIMIN and MAXIMAX methods;
- Methods using information on criteria. This group is very large, and is discussed separately;
- Methods using information on alternatives. Pairwise preference methods include LINMAP and interactive / iterative SAW. Pairwise proximity methods include MDS (multidimensional scaling) with ideal point and MRS (marginal rate of substitution) with ideal point.

The methods using information on criteria are further divided according to the salient features of the information:

- Thresholds (cut-off levels) of each criterion. CONJUNCTIVE and DISJUNCTIVE methods;

- Relative importance of each criterion by ordinal preference. LEXICOGRAPHIC ordering; ELIMINATION BY ASPECTS; PERMUTATION method;
- Relative importance of each criterion by cardinal preference. LINEAR ASSIGNMENT, SAW (simple additive weighting), HSAW (hierarchical SAW), TOPSIS, VIKOR, COPRAS, ARAS, MOORA, ELECTRE, PROMETHEUS, ORESTE;
- Marginal rate of substitution (MRS) between criteria. Marginal rate of substitution, Indifference curves, Hierarchical trade-offs.

The conjunctive and disjunctive methods are screening methods where the performance values of the alternatives must exceed given thresholds (cut-off levels) on the criteria.

5.4.2.4. MCDM methods according to type of data

MCDM methods can be classified by type of data into the following groups:

- Deterministic (or “crisp”).
- Non-deterministic, e.g. stochastic or fuzzy.

Data refers to the evaluations of the alternatives on the criteria.

5.4.2.5. Other classifications

Belton & Stewart (2001) and Bana e Costa et al. (1997) identify three broad categories:

- Goals, aspiration or reference level models. The decision-maker finds it difficult to express trade-offs (criteria weights). Alternatives are systematically eliminated until a satisfactory performance level for a criterion has been ensured. Bana e Costa et al. (1997) refer to “interactive methods”, where interactions between decision-maker and analyst focus on progressively decreasing the number of alternatives;
- Value measurement models. The values of the alternatives reflect a preference order, and those preferences are required to be consistent with a set of axioms. Bana e Costa et al. (1997) refer to “aggregation approaches”;
- Outranking models. Pairwise evaluations of alternatives assess preferences and indifferences as well as identify incomparability.

Wang et al (2009); Fülöp (2005); and Yevseyeva (2012) distinguish

- Elementary methods. Pros and cons analysis; DOMINANCE; MAXIMIN; MAXIMAX; Hurwicz’s criterion method; CONJUNCTIVE and DISJUNCTIVE methods; LEXICOGRAPHIC method; ELIMINATION BY ASPECTS; weighted sum (SAW); weighted product; LINEAR ASSIGNMENT], ...
- Unique synthesizing criteria | MAUT methods | American School. MAUT/MAVT; SMART; TOPSIS; generalized means; grey relational analysis; DEA; UTA (“UTilités Additives”); AHP; ...
- Outranking methods | European school. ELECTRE; PROMETHEE; ORESTE; ...
- Group decision making.

Elementary methods are simple and no computational support is needed. The MAUT methods consist of aggregating the different criteria into a function (a “single criterion of synthesis”), which has to be maximized. The weights of the criteria reflect the importance of the criteria, but the performance levels of the alternatives on all criteria have to be transformed to a common dimensionless scale. This transformation can be factual (objective, quantitative) or judgmental (subjective, qualitative) (Fülöp, 2005).

We will use the following taxonomy, based on Fulop (2005).

BASIC TECHNIQUES

Pros and cons analysis

Basic Methods for problems without any information about criteria or about decision alternatives:

- The Dominance method
- The MaxiMin method
- The Maximax method

Basic Methods using information about criteria

- Conjunctive and Disjunctive approaches
- Lexicographic methods
- [Elimination by aspects](#)
- Simple Additive Weighting (SAW)
- [Multiplicative weighting](#)

CLASSICAL APPROACHES (“American school”)

- MAUT/MAVT
- SMART
- The Even Swaps method
- TOPSIS
- AHP

OUTRANKING APPROACHES (“European school”)

- PROMETHEE
- ELECTRE

5.4.3. Basic techniques

5.4.3.1. Pros and cons analysis

Pros and cons analysis is a qualitative comparison method in which good things (pros) and bad things (cons) are identified about each alternative. Lists of the pros and cons, based on the input of subject matter experts, are compared one to another for each alternative. The alternative with the strongest pros and weakest cons is preferred. The decision documentation should include an exposition, which justifies why the preferred alternative’s pros are more important and its cons are less consequential than those of the other alternatives ([US-DOE, 2001](#)).

Pros and cons analysis is suitable for simple decisions with few alternatives (2 to 4) and few discriminating criteria (1 to 5) of approximately equal value. It requires no mathematical skill and can be implemented rapidly ([US-DOE, 2001](#)).

5.4.3.2. The dominance method

A limited amount of information about the relative merits of the alternatives can be obtained by direct inspection of the performance matrix. The dominance method consists of the following steps ([Xiaoqian, 2012](#)):

- Compare the first two alternatives and if one is dominated by the other, discard the dominated one;
- Next, compare the undiscarded alternative with the third alternative and discard any dominated alternative;
- Then, compare the fourth alternative and so on;
- After all the alternatives are compared, the non-dominated set is determined.

The dominance method can be used for selection, screening, or short-listing ([Communities UK, 2009](#)):

- Choice. If an alternative dominates all others, it is the best available. In theory, one alternative might dominate all others. In practice, this is unlikely;
- Screening. Dominance enables the decision-maker to eliminate dominated alternative from further consideration. If alternative A dominates alternative B, then B cannot be the single best one available. If the purpose of the MCDA is to recommend a single best alternative, B may be removed from consideration;
- Short-listing. It is unlikely that a dominated alternative would be taken through to a later stage in the selection process. Logically, it would only make sense to do so if it was thought that new information about alternatives might come to light, that some of the criteria scores might be inaccurate, or if there was some possibility that the dominating alternative might cease to be available.

The dominance method makes no assumptions about the relative importance of criteria. It does not employ any supplementary information beyond that directly displayed in the decision matrix. Dominance assessments (based on a series of yes/no calculations) can be sensitive to errors in the data in the decision matrix. The dominance assessments are potentially changed by the addition or removal of even a single alternative. The non-dominated set usually has multiple alternatives.

5.4.3.3. The maximin method

The maximin method is based upon a strategy that tries to avoid the worst possible performance, maximizing the minimal performing criterion (the “maximin”).

The overall performance of an alternative is determined by the weakest or poorest criterion. The decision-maker examines the criteria values for each alternative, notes the worst value for each alternative, and then selects the alternative with the most acceptable value in its worst criterion (Xiaoqian, 2012).

$$A^* = \left\{ A_i \mid \max_i \min_j x_{ij} \right\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

The maximin method can be used only when all criteria are comparable so that they can be measured on a common scale (Fülop, 2005).

5.4.3.4. The maximax method

The maximax method selects an alternative by its best criterion value rather than its worst criterion value. The best criterion value for each alternative is identified. The maximum values are compared in order to select the alternative with the best value

$$A^* = \left\{ A_i \mid \max_i \max_j x_{ij} \right\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

The maximax (and maximin) methods utilize only a small part of the available information in making a final choice (only one criterion per alternative).

5.4.3.5. Conjunctive and disjunctive methods

The conjunctive and disjunctive methods allow the introduction of performance levels (“thresholds” or “cut-offs”) for one or more criteria. The supplementary information that complements the information in the decision matrix consists of the thresholds themselves and, implicitly, a judgement that the criteria concerned justify being prioritised in this way over others for which no thresholds may be given (Communities UK, 2009).

- The conjunctive model eliminates alternatives that fail to meet externally set levels of performance on each of one or more named criteria.
- The disjunctive model allows an alternative to pass if the alternative concerned meets a minimum threshold level of performance on at least one of a set of named criteria .

These methods require satisfactory rather than best performance in each criterion (Fülop, 2005).

5.4.3.6. Lexicographic methods

The decision-maker provides supplementary information about the ranking of criteria in terms of perceived importance. The lexicographic method considers each criterion in turn and works as a sequential elimination model (Communities UK, 2009).

The criteria are ranked in the order of their importance. The alternative with the best performance score on the most important criterion is chosen. If there are ties with respect to this criterion, the performance of the tied alternatives on the next most important criterion will be compared, and so on, until a unique alternative is found (Fülop, 2005).

The preference information on the criteria does not have to be in numerical values. The method only uses a small part of the available information in making a final decision (Xiaoqian, 2012).

5.4.3.7. Elimination by Aspects

This elimination by aspects model combines elements of both the conjunctive/disjunctive models and lexicographic ordering.

The decision-maker sets a threshold or cut-off (minimum performance level) for each criterion. A criterion is selected, and all alternatives that do not pass the cut-off on that criterion are eliminated. Then another criterion is selected, and so forth. The process continues until all alternatives but one are eliminated (Xiaoqian, 2012)

The criteria are examined not in order of importance, but in perceived order of likelihood of maximising the number of options that fail to pass (Communities UK, 2009).

5.4.3.8. Weighted Sum Method (WSM) – Simple Additive Weighting (SAW)

The simple additive weighting (SAW) method (Fishburn, 1967), also known as the “weighted sum method” (WSM) or the “linear (additive) model”, shows how the values of an alternative on the many criteria can be combined into one overall value. This is done by multiplying the value score on each criterion by the weight of that criterion, and then adding all those weighted scores together (Communities UK, 2009).

All scales are either to be minimized or to be maximized. All scales are to be normalized, i.e. homogenized for commensurable comparison. We refer to the chapter on “normalization”.

The score of an alternative A_i is calculated as the weighted sum of the criteria scores according to their predefined weighting factors.

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Where

m is the number of alternatives

n is the number of criteria

w_j is the relative weight of importance of the criterion C_j

x_{ij} is the performance value of alternative A_i in terms of criterion C_j

It is usually assumed that $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

The resulting cardinal scores for each alternative can be used to rank, screen, or choose an alternative. The best alternative is the one whose score is the maximum.

The advantages of the SAW model are that it is simple and intuitive, it is very efficient (computationally speaking), and it generates a strongly non-dominated solution that can be used as an initial solution for other techniques (Palesi, 2006).

SAW is difficult for qualitative scales. It requires all the criterion values to be both numerical and comparable. This triggers the normalization problem of all the elements in decision matrix. The quantification methods and normalization methods will have a significant influence on the final decision results (Xiaoqian, 2012).

SAW is sensitive to the weighting factors. Results can vary significantly as the weighting coefficients change. A sensitivity analysis with many different values of the weights is required (Palesi, 2006).

Adding or removing alternatives may change ranking.

This simple arithmetic of the SAW method is only appropriate if the criteria are mutually preference independent. The assumption of mutual independence of preferences means that the judged strength of preference for an option on one criterion will be independent of its judged strength of preference on another (Communities UK, 2009).

The solution often appears only in some parts of the Pareto front, while no solutions are obtained in other parts. SAW cannot find a solution on the non-convex parts of the Pareto front. SAW does not allow convex combination of objectives where the sum of all weights is constant. It does not allow negative weights (Palesi, 2006).

5.4.3.9. Weighted Product Method (WPM) – Multiplicative Weighting method

The weighted product method (WPM), also known as the “multiplicative weighting method”, is similar to simple additive weighting method (SAW).

The score of an alternative A_i is calculated as follows:

$$S_i = \prod_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^{w_j} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

The best alternative is the one whose score is the maximum.

It may be convenient to compare the score of each alternative with a “standard score”.

$$R_i = \frac{S_i}{S^*} = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^{w_j}}{\prod_{j=1}^n x_{j^*}^{w_j}} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Where x_{j^*} is the most favourable performance for criterion C_j .

All criterion values or ratings have to be greater than 1, given the exponentiation property. When a criterion value is smaller than one (fractional rating), all the criterion values or ratings in that criterion should be multiplied by 10^k , where k is an exponent which makes the smallest criterion value bigger than one.

5.4.4. Classical approaches

5.4.4.1. Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) – Multi-Attribute Value Theory (MAVT)

Multi-attribute utility theory (MAUT) is derived from the work of von Neumann and Morgenstern and of Savage in the 1940s and 1950s. Their work provides powerful theoretical insights, but does not directly help decision makers in undertaking complex multi-criteria decision tasks.

Keeney and Raiffa (1976) developed a set of procedures, consistent with the earlier normative foundations, which would allow decision makers to evaluate multi-criteria options in practice. This method is known as multi-attribute value theory (MAVT). The basis is the existence of a real valued function U , defined on the set A of feasible alternatives. The value function theory is based on the utility maximisation concept.

5.4.4.1.1. The performance matrix

The decision maker seeks to achieve his objectives. The set of alternatives $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\}$ is finite and known. The alternatives are the potential solutions to the decision problem. The set of criteria (or “attributes”) $g_j(\cdot)$ allows the measurement of the performance levels of the alternatives. A number

$v_j[g_j(a_i)]$ or $v_j(a_i)$ can be assigned to each performance level of alternative a_i on the criterion or “attribute” $g_j(a_i)$. MAVT can thus be seen as a quantitative decision method. The alternatives can be compared through numbers.

Figure 9 The performance matrix in MAVT

	$g_1(\cdot)$	$g_2(\cdot)$...	$g_n(\cdot)$
	k_1	k_2	...	k_n
a_1	$v_1(a_1)$	$v_2(a_1)$...	$v_n(a_1)$
a_2	$v_1(a_2)$	$v_2(a_1)$...	$v_n(a_2)$
...
a_m	$v_1(a_m)$	$v_2(a_1)$...	$v_n(a_m)$

The decision maker expresses how important each criterion or attribute is to him. This means that weights have to be assigned. The number k_j is the importance coefficient of criterion (“attribute”) $g_j(\cdot)$. In most of the MAVT based approaches, the weights associated with the criteria can properly reflect the relative importance of the criteria only if the scores $v_j(a_i)$ are from a common, dimensionless scale. The MAVT procedures do not prescribe a particular weighting method (see also chapter on “weighting”).

The basis of MAVT is the existence of a real valued function U , defined on the set A of feasible alternatives. The set of MAVT methods consists of aggregating the different criteria into a function, which has to be maximized. The decision maker wants to optimise his aggregate value function U . The decision problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\max U[g_j(a)] : a \in A, \forall g_j(a), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

5.4.4.1.2. The value functions

The value function is a mathematical representation of human judgements, defining the subjective preferences of the decision maker, and thus allowing an analytical study of preferences. A real number is associated with each alternative, to construct a preference order of the alternatives consistent with the decision-maker’s value judgments. The preferences are required to be consistent with a relatively strong set of axioms, namely:

- Preferences are complete. For any pair of alternatives, either one is strictly preferred to the other or there is indifference between them;
- Preferences and indifferences are transitive.

A value function is assessed for each criterion or attribute $g_j(\cdot)$ separately. The idea is to build a function that the decision-maker perceives as adequate to represent his judgment about strengths of preference. The absolute number of the score is meaningless, what counts is the difference (De montis et al, 2000).

There are different techniques for constructing criteria value functions, for instance direct rating, curve fitting, bisections or standard differences (Yevseyeva, 2012).

There are different techniques for constructing criteria value functions, for instance (Yevseyeva, 2012):

- Direct rating. The decision-maker has to provide a numerical value for each performance level on a given criterion’s scale. Or he can adjust a graphical representation of performance levels on a line segment representing value;
- Curve fitting. The decision-maker has to adjust the parameters that define a given curve. The given curve might for example be a negative exponential curve ranging from extremely concave to extremely convex cases; or a sigmoid curve;
- Bisection. The decision maker has to indicate a performance level that corresponds to the best value and set it to 1; and the worst value and set it to 0. Next, the decision maker has to indicate a performance level that splits the interval in two in terms of value (such that changing

from the 0 value performance to the chosen midpoint increases value as much as does changing from this midpoint to the 1 value performance). The chosen midpoint corresponds to value 0.5. The same process is used to bisect the intervals [0, 0.5] and [0.5, 1], and so forth.

- Standard differences. The analyst defines an improvement in a different criterion to serve as a comparison standard (or „ruler“). The analyst takes an initial value $v_j(a^1)$ in criterion $g_j(\cdot)$. The decision maker has to indicate a second value $v_j(a^2)$ such that the increase in value of going from $v_j(a^1)$ to $v_j(a^2)$ is equal to the comparison standard defined before. Next the decision maker indicates a third value such that the increase in value of going from $v_j(a^2)$ to $v_j(a^3)$ is equal to the comparison standard defined before, and so forth. Then $v_j(a^2) - v_j(a^1) = v_j(a^3) - v_j(a^2) = \dots$

5.4.4.1.3. The aggregate (value) function

The criteria values for each alternative are aggregated $U(a_i) = f(v_1(a_i), \dots, v_j(a_i), \dots, v_n(a_i))$.

Figure 10 A user-defined partial value function (for a benefit criterion)

The aggregated function $U(A)$ aggregates the unidimensional functions representing preferences (human judgements) on each single criterion (or attribute) taken separately.

The aggregated value function in most cases takes an additive (linear) or multiplicative form. Both the additive and multiplicative model require independence of the criteria (attributes). The most general form is the multilinear model, which in addition to the criteria (attribute) weights contains so-called interaction coefficients for modelling the interactions between two or more criteria (attributes).

- The multilinear model can be written $U(a_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n k_j v_j(a_i) + \sum_{j_1=1}^n \sum_{j_2>j_1}^n k_{j_1} v_{j_1}(a_i) I_{j_1 j_2} k_{j_2} v_{j_2}(a_i) + \dots + I_{j_1 \dots j_n} \prod_{j=1}^n k_j v_j(a_i)$ where $U(a_i)$ is the aggregated value function; k_j are the criteria (attribute) weights; $v_j(a_i)$ are the value functions; and $I_{j_1 j_2}$, $I_{j_1 j_2 j_3}$, $I_{j_1 \dots j_n}$ are the interaction coefficients. The normalization constraint is given by $\sum_{j=1}^n k_j + \sum_{j_1=1}^n \sum_{j_2>j_1}^n k_{j_1} I_{j_1 j_2} k_{j_2} + \dots + I_{j_1 \dots j_n} \prod_{j=1}^n k_j = 1$
- The additive model can be derived from the multilinear model by setting all interaction coefficients to zero. An additive (linear) function can be written $U(a_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n k_j v_j(a_i)$ with $k_j > 0 \forall j$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n k_j = 1$.
- The multiplicative model can be derived from the multilinear model by setting all interaction coefficients to one constant. The scaling constants are replaced such that $I_{j_1 j_2} = I$, $I_{j_1 j_2 j_3} = I^2$

up to $I_{j_1 \dots j_n} = I^{n-1}$. The multiplicative function can be written $U(a_i) = I^{n-1} \{ \prod_{j=1}^n [1 + I k_j v_j(a_i)] - 1 \}$. The normalization constraint is $1 + I = \prod_{j=1}^n (1 + I k_j)$

The additive model is the most commonly used form in practice.

The advantage of the additive (linear) form is its simplicity. It matches the intuitive way individuals aggregate. The MAVT procedures are a rigorous way of obtaining commensurable scales. The MAVT model is compensatory. MAVT shows the role of “weights” as trade-offs. There is an underlying compensation effect, in the sense that bad performances in some criteria may be compensated by good performances in other criteria. Complete compensation among all attributes is usually allowed.

The linear assumption might be too restrictive for a lot of decision problems, as it requires strong independence conditions (but it may be possible to restructure the set of criteria).

The MAVT method can be difficult to explain. The difficulties lie primarily in the estimation of the aggregate value function U.

5.4.4.2. Simple multiattribute rating technique (SMART)

SMART is the simplest form of the MAUT methods. The ranking value $R(a_i)$ of alternative a_i is obtained simply as the weighted algebraic mean of the utility values associated with it.

$$R(a_i) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n k_j v_j(a_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^n k_j}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

The SMART method also consist of a simple method to assess the weights for each of the criteria reflect its relative importance to the decision. We refer to the chapter on “weighting”.

5.4.4.3. The Even Swaps method

The even swaps method was initially proposed by Hammond, Keeney and Raiffa (1998).The even swaps method for preference elicitation is an elimination process based on value trade-offs which are called “even swaps” (Mustajoki, 2006).

Figure 11 The Even Swap process

The decision maker changes the consequence of an alternative on one criterion (attribute), and compensates this change with a preferentially equal change in the consequence of another criterion (attribute). This creates a new virtual alternative with revised consequences. This is as preferred as the initial one, and thus it can be used as a surrogate, even though it is not a real alternative.

The aim of the even swaps process is to carry out even swaps that either make criteria (attributes) irrelevant or alternatives dominated.

- A criterion (attribute) is irrelevant if all the alternatives have equal consequences on this criterion (attribute);
- An alternative A dominates alternative B if A is better than or equal to B on every criterion (attribute), and better at least on one criterion (attribute).

The irrelevant criteria (attributes) and dominated alternatives can both be eliminated, and the process continues until only the most preferred alternative remains.

The even swaps method also introduces the concept of “practical dominance”. Alternative A practically dominates alternative B if B is slightly better than A on only one or few criteria (attributes) but A clearly outranks B on several other criteria (attributes). Thus, B can be eliminated in order to reduce the problem.

The even swaps method is a conceptually simple process. The decision maker does not need to have a mathematical or decision analytical background to use the method. For example, the decision maker does not have to explicitly define the preferences over the criteria (attributes) in general or to make any assumptions about the form of the value function.

The interpretation of the results in the even swaps process is not as transparent as in traditional multi-attribute value theory (MAVT) approaches.

5.4.4.4. Technique of Order Preference by Similarity of Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)

The TOPSIS method was initially proposed by Hwang and Yoon (1981). The basic principle of the TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) method is that the chosen alternatives should have the shortest (Euclidean) distance (in a geometrical sense) from the positive-ideal solution; and the farthest distance from the negative-ideal solution. The positive-ideal solution is a *hypothetical* solution for which all criteria (attribute) values correspond to the maximum criteria (attribute) values in the feasible solution space. The negative-ideal solution is a hypothetical solution for which all criteria (attribute) values correspond to the minimum criteria (attribute) values in the feasible solution space

Figure 12 The TOPSIS method

Source: Xiaoqian, 2012.

TOPSIS requires a decision matrix and relative weights as input data. The TOPSIS procedure consists of the following steps:

- Normalize the decision matrix;
- Calculate the weighted normalized decision matrix;
- Identify the positive ideal solution and the negative ideal solution;
- Calculate the distance of each alternative to the positive-ideal solution and the negative-ideal solution;

- Calculate the relative closeness of each alternative to the ideal solutions;
- Rank the alternatives according to the value of their relative closeness.

TOPSIS has a fairly intuitive physical meaning based on the consideration of distances from ideal solutions. TOPSIS is able to identify the best alternative fairly quickly. TOPSIS has been shown to be one of the best MADM methods in addressing the rank reversal issue (the change in the ranking of alternatives when a non-optimal alternative is introduced).

The TOPSIS method assumes that each criterion has monotonically increasing or decreasing utility. This makes it easy to locate the ideal and negative ideal solutions. The TOPSIS method is fairly sensitive to the weighting factors; and can give unreliable results. TOPSIS in its standard form is deterministic and does not consider uncertainty in weightings.

5.4.4.5. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) was developed by Saaty (1977). The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) is a quantitative comparison method used to select a preferred alternative by using pair-wise comparisons of the alternatives based on their relative performance against the criteria. The basis of this technique is that humans are more capable of making relative judgements than absolute judgements (US-DOE, 2001).

AHP is a type of weighted sum method (WSM). The AHP weighting method is described in the chapter on "weighting". AHP decomposes a decision-making problem into a system of hierarchies. The criteria are often arranged in a tree-structure. Each performance at a given level is multiplied with its weight and the weighted performances are summed to get the score at a higher level. The procedure is repeated upward for each hierarchy, until the top of the hierarchy is reached. The alternative with the highest score is the best alternative.

AHP uses procedures for deriving the scores achieved by the alternatives and for the weights which are based, respectively, on pairwise comparisons between alternatives and criteria.

Alternatives and criteria are scored using a pairwise comparison method and mathematics. The pairwise comparisons are made using a nine-point scale:

- 1 = Equal importance or preference
- 3 = Moderate importance or preference of one over another
- 5 = Strong or essential importance or preference
- 7 = Very strong or demonstrated importance or preference
- 9 = Extreme importance or preference

The procedure (at a single level) uses the following steps (US-DOE, 2001):

- Pairwise comparison matrices are developed wherein each criterion / alternative is compared against the others. If criterion C_A is strongly more important compared to criterion C_B (i.e. a value of "5"), then criterion C_B has a value of 1/5 compared to criterion C_A . For each comparative score given, the reciprocal is awarded to the opposite relationship. If m is the number of alternatives and n the number of criteria, there will be $n(m \times m)$ matrices in total;
- The "priority vector" (i.e. the normalized weight) is calculated for each criterion using the geometric mean of each row in the matrix divided by the sum of the geometric means of all the criteria;
- The process is repeated for the alternatives comparing them one to another to determine their relative value / importance for each criterion (i.e. to determine the normalized alternative score).
- To identify the preferred alternative each normalized score of an alternative is multiplied by the corresponding normalized criterion weight, and summed;
- The preferred alternative has the highest total score.

AHP has an intuitive appeal and decision makers generally find the pair wise comparison form of data input straightforward and convenient. The AHP calculations are not complex.

AHP assumes preference independence at any level except for the bottom level. It would be problematic to use AHP where the criteria at the same level have correlated dependence;

The complete pairwise comparison is not a trivial task for the decision maker and may trigger inconsistency problems. These problems will become worse with the increasing dimension of the pairwise comparison matrix. The number of pairwise comparisons may become very large.

The use of the 9-point scale is an artificial limitation. The decision maker may find it difficult to distinguish between them.

AHP is a controversial technique in the operations research (OR) community. The theoretical basis of AHP is questioned as the underlying axioms on which AHP is based are not sufficiently clear as to be empirically testable. More in particular, doubts have been raised about the *rank reversal* phenomenon. A new alternative, which is added to an otherwise unchanged decision problem, may cause a reordering of the previous rank order. The proponents of AHP claim that rank reversals caused by inconsistency are natural and acceptable.

5.4.5. Outranking methods

The outranking methods are methods based on – crisp or fuzzy – pairwise comparisons of alternatives in order to decide if one alternative in a pair is preferred, indifferent or incomparable to the other alternative in the pair, according to the decision maker's preferences. In such comparisons, a disadvantage in one criterion sometimes cannot be compensated by advantages in other criteria (de Souza, 2011).

All alternatives are assessed in terms of the extent to which they exhibit sufficient outranking with respect to the full set of alternatives being considered as measured against a pair of threshold parameters.

Based on this rather general idea, a series of procedures have been developed to operationalise outranking as a way of supporting multi-criteria decision making (MCDM). Typically, they involve two phases (Communities UK, 2009):

- Specifying a precise way of determining whether one alternative outranks another;
- Determining how all the pairwise outranking assessments can be combined to suggest an overall preference ranking among the options.

It is possible with outranking methods that, under certain conditions, two alternatives are classified as "difficult to compare". That might be associated with missing information at the time the assessment is made.

The outranking approach is dependent on some rather arbitrary definitions of what precisely constitutes outranking and how the threshold parameters are set and later manipulated by the decision maker (Communities UK, 2009).

5.4.5.1. ELECTRE ("Elimination et Choix Traduisant la Realite")

The "Elimination et Choix Traduisant la Realite" (ELECTRE) method was initially proposed by Roy (1991). The ELECTRE method is a family (ELECTRE I, ELECTRE IS, ELECTRE II, ELECTRE III, ELECTRE IV and ELECTRE TRI) of outranking methods developed to rank a set of alternatives.

The ELECTRE methods are based on pairwise comparisons. Given an ordered pair of alternatives (a, b), the method seeks to find whether there are sufficient arguments to assert that "a outranks b". The outranking relation S is the basis to find the preference relations. The outranking relation is constructed based on two concepts:

- Concordance: If $g_j(a)$ is not worse than $g_j(b)$, then the criterion $g_j(\cdot)$ is concordant with a S b
- Discordance: If $g_j(a)$ is worse than $g_j(b)$, then the criterion $g_j(\cdot)$ is discordant with a S b.

The processes of building outranking relations vary according to the ELECTRE method.

The outranking relation is evaluated for all pairs of alternatives, in both directions: $a S b$ and $b S a$. Note that a criterion can be concordant with both $a S b$ and $b S a$, namely when $g_j(a) = g_j(b)$.

After evaluating the outranking relation, four situations may occur, defining three preference relations:

- $a P b$ (a is strictly preferred to b), if $a S b$ and $\neg b S a$
- $b P a$ (a is strictly preferred to b), if $b S a$ and $\neg a S b$
- $a R b$ (a is incomparable to b), if $\neg a S b$ and $\neg b S a$
- $a I b$ (a is indifferent to b), if $a S b$ and $b S a$

An outranking method may not render the best alternative directly. A subset of alternatives can be determined such that any alternative not in the subset is outranked by at least one member of the subset. The aim is to make the subset of alternatives as small as possible, which can be considered as a shortlist.

For illustrative purposes, we give a brief description of the ELECTRE I method.

5.4.5.1.1. Step 1. Calculate the normalized decision matrix

Each element of the normalized ($m \times n$) decision matrix R is calculated as $r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}$ $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ where m is the number of alternatives and n is the number of criteria.

5.4.5.1.2. Step 2. Calculate the weighted normalized decision matrix

Each element of the weighted normalized matrix V is calculated by multiplying each row of the normalized matrix R with its associated weight. $v_{ij} = w_j r_{ij}$ $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

5.4.5.1.3. Step 3. Determine the concordance and discordance set

For each pair of alternatives A_k and A_l the set of decision criteria $J = \{j | j = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is divided into two disjoint subsets. The concordance set C_{kl} of A_k and A_l is composed of all criteria for which A_k is preferred to A_l . The discordance set D_{kl} is the complementary set of the concordance set.

$$C_{kl} = \{j | x_{kj} \geq x_{lj}\} \quad k, l = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad k \neq l$$

$$D_{kl} = \{j | x_{kj} < x_{lj}\} = J - C_{kl}$$

5.4.5.1.4. Step 4. Calculate the concordance matrix

Each element c_{kl} of the ($n \times n$) concordance matrix C is calculated by the sum of the criteria weights contained in the concordance set C_{kl} .

$$c_{kl} = \frac{\sum_{j \in C_{kl}} w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j} \quad 0 \leq c_{kl} \leq 1$$

If $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$ then $c_{kl} = \sum_{j \in C_{kl}} w_j$, i.e. the concordance index for the ordered pair of alternatives (A_k, A_l) is simply the sum of all the weights for those criteria where alternative A_k performs at least as good as alternative A_l .

The concordance index c_{kl} reflects the degree at which the evaluation of alternative A_k is better than the evaluation of alternative A_l . A higher value of c_{kl} indicates A_k is more preferred to A_l according to the concordance criteria. The concordance matrix C is in general not symmetric.

5.4.5.1.5. Step 5. Calculate the discordance matrix

Each element d_{kl} of the ($n \times n$) discordance matrix D is defined as

$$d_{kl} = \frac{\max_{j \in D_{kl}} |v_{kj} - v_{lj}|}{\max_{j \in J} |v_{kj} - v_{lj}|} \quad 0 \leq d_{kl} \leq 1$$

where v_{ij} are elements of the weighted normalized matrix V .

The discordance index d_{kl} reflects the degree at which the evaluation of alternative A_k is worse than the evaluation of alternative A_l . A higher value of d_{kl} indicates that A_k is less pre-

ferred to A_l according to the discordance criteria. The concordance matrix D is in general not symmetric.

5.4.5.1.6. Step 6. Determine the concordance dominance matrix

A (relatively high) threshold value \bar{c} of the concordance index c_{kl} needs to be chosen to perform the concordance test. Alternative A_k will dominate alternative A_l only if its corresponding concordance index c_{kl} exceeds a certain threshold value \bar{c} , that is if $c_{kl} \geq \bar{c}$. The threshold value \bar{c} can be determined in many ways.

Each element f_{kl} of the $(n \times n)$ concordance dominance matrix F is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} c_{kl} \geq \bar{c} &\rightarrow f_{kl} = 1 \\ c_{kl} < \bar{c} &\rightarrow f_{kl} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Each element of 1 in the Boolean matrix F thus represents a dominance of one alternative over another.

5.4.5.1.7. Step 7. Determine the discordance dominance

A (relatively low) threshold value \bar{d} of the discordance index d_{kl} needs to be chosen to perform the discordance test. Alternative A_k will dominate alternative A_l only if its corresponding discordance index d_{kl} is smaller than a certain threshold value \bar{d} , that is if $d_{kl} \leq \bar{d}$. The threshold value \bar{d} can be determined in many ways.

Each element g_{kl} of the $(n \times n)$ discordance dominance matrix G is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} d_{kl} \leq \bar{d} &\rightarrow g_{kl} = 1 \\ d_{kl} > \bar{d} &\rightarrow g_{kl} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Each element of 1 in the Boolean matrix G thus represents a dominance of one alternative over another.

5.4.5.1.8. Step 8. Determine the aggregate dominance matrix

The $(n \times n)$ aggregate dominance matrix E is the intersection of the concordance dominance matrix F and the discordance dominance matrix G . Each element e_{kl} of the $(n \times n)$ aggregate dominance matrix E is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{kl} = 1 \wedge g_{kl} = 1 &\rightarrow e_{kl} = 1 \\ e_{kl} &= 0 \text{ otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

An alternative A_k outranks alternative A_l if the concordance index c_{kl} of A_k lies above the chosen threshold value \bar{c} and its discordance index d_{kl} lies below the threshold value \bar{d} .

5.4.5.1.9. Step 9. Eliminate the dominated alternatives

The aggregate dominance matrix E gives the partial preference ordering of the alternatives. If $e_{kl} = 1$ then A_k is preferred to A_l for both the concordance and discordance criteria, but A_k may still be dominated by other alternatives. The condition that A_k is not dominated is that

$$\begin{aligned} e_{kl} &= 1 \text{ for at least one } l, l = 1, 2, \dots, n; k \neq l \\ e_{ik} &= 0 \text{ for all } i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n; i \neq k, k \neq l \end{aligned}$$

In the aggregated dominance matrix the element 1 in a column indicates that the corresponding alternative is dominated by another alternative. Therefore, any alternative which has at least one element of 1 in the aggregate dominance matrix can be eliminated. The resulting set of alternatives is the set of all alternatives that outrank at least one other alternative and are themselves not outranked. If the set is too small (large), it can be expanded (contracted) by appropriate changes to the concordance and/or discordance thresholds.

ELECTRE allows to take into account quantitative and qualitative criteria. It operates with simple logic, uses a systematic computational procedure, and is able to detect the presence of incomparability between alternatives.

ELECTRE does not have a strong axiomatic basis. There is no compensation effect. A loss in one criterion cannot be compensated by a gain in another criterion.

The ELECTRE methods are rather complex to implement in real world problems.

5.4.5.2. PROMETHEE (Preference Ranking Organization METHOD for Enrichment Evaluations)

The “Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluations” or PROMETHEE method was first introduced by Brans (1982). The PROMETHEE method is a family (PROMETHEE I, II,III, IV,V an VI) of methods.

PROMETHEE I provides a partial preorder on all alternatives. PROMETHEE II offers a complete preorder on all alternatives. We briefly discuss PROMETHEE II.

The decision matrix is the starting point of the PROMETHEE methodology. The scores x_{ij} need not necessarily be normalized or transformed into a common dimensionless scale. It is further assumed that a higher score means a better performance; and the weights w_j of the criteria have been determined by the appropriate method (PROMETHEE does not define a preferred weighting method).

The central principle of PROMETHEE II is based on the pairwise comparison of alternatives along each criterion (attribute) that is to be maximised or minimised.

5.4.5.2.1. Building the outranking relation

The implementation of PROMETHEE II requires relevant information concerning the preference functions of the criteria (attributes). For each criterion, the preference function translates the difference between the evaluations obtained by two alternatives into a preference degree ranging from 0 to 1.

A preference function is associated to each criterion. A preference function $P_j(A_k, A_l)$ is defined, representing the degree of the preference of alternative A_k over A_l for criterion C_j . PROMETHEE considers the degree of preference in normalized form, so that $0 \leq P_j(A_k, A_l) \leq 1$ and

- $P_j(A_k, A_l) = 0$ means no preference or an indifference between A_k and A_l
- $P_j(A_k, A_l) \approx 0$ means weak preference of A_k over A_l
- $P_j(A_k, A_l) \approx 1$ means strong preference of A_k over A_l
- $P_j(A_k, A_l) = 1$ means strict preference of A_k over A_l

In most practical cases, $P_j(A_k, A_l)$ is a function of the deviations $d = (a_{kj} - a_{lj})$. That is, $P_j(A_k, A_l) = p_j(a_{kj} - a_{lj})$, where p_j is a non-decreasing function, $p_j(d) = 0$ for $d \leq 0$ and $0 \leq p_j(d) \leq 1$ for $d > 0$.

The decision-maker has to define a preference threshold c_j^p and an indifference threshold for each criterion c_j^i . To facilitate the selection of a specific preference function, six basic or generalized types of criteria are proposed or recommended.

Usual criterion. $P_j(A_k, A_l) = \begin{cases} 0 & \forall d \leq 0 \\ 1 & \forall d > 0 \end{cases}$

U-shape criterion or quasi criterion. $P_j(A_k, A_l) = \begin{cases} 0 & \forall d \leq c_j^i \\ 1 & \forall d > c_j^i \end{cases}$

V-shape criterion or criterion with linear preference. $P_j(A_k, B) = \begin{cases} 0 & d \leq 0 \\ \frac{d}{c_j^p} & 0 \leq d \leq c_j^p \\ 1 & d \leq c_j^p \end{cases}$

Level criterion. $P_j(A_k, A_l) = \begin{cases} 0 & d \leq c_j^i \\ 0.5 & c_j^i < d \leq c_j^p \\ 1 & d > c_j^p \end{cases}$

V-shape with indifference criterion. $P_j(A_k, A_l) = \begin{cases} 0 & d \leq c_j^I \\ \frac{d-c_j^I}{c_j^P-c_j^I} & c_j^I \leq d \leq c_j^P \\ 1 & d \geq c_j^P \end{cases}$

Gaussian criterion. $P_j(A_k, A_l) = \begin{cases} 0 & d \leq 0 \\ 1 - e^{\left(\frac{-d^2}{2\sigma_j^2}\right)} & d > 0 \end{cases}$

These six types of criteria are particularly easy to define.

Figure 13 Types of criteria in PROMETHEE

Source: Xiaoqian, 2012.

5.4.5.2.2. Multi-criteria preference index

A multicriteria preference index $\pi(A_k, A_l)$ of A_k over A_l is defined, considering all the criteria.

$$\pi(A_k, A_l) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j P_j(A_k, A_l)$$

With $0 \leq \pi(A_k, A_l) \leq 1$. The multicriteria preference index represents the global intensity of preference between the ordered pair of alternatives.

5.4.5.2.3. Exploiting the outranking relation

To rank the m alternatives, PROMETHEE defines two precedence flows, a positive outranking flow (“leaving flow”) and a negative outranking flow (“entering flow”).

The positive outranking flow Φ^+ expresses how much each alternative is outranking all the other alternatives.

$$\Phi^+(A_k) = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{l=1}^m \pi(A_k, A_l)$$

The negative outranking flow Φ^- expresses how much each alternative is outranked by the other alternatives.

$$\Phi^-(A_k) = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{l=1}^m \pi(A_l, A_k)$$

5.4.5.2.4. The PROMETHEE I partial ranking

- A_k is preferred to A_l if $\Phi^+(A_k) \geq \Phi^+(A_l)$, $\Phi^-(A_k) \leq \Phi^-(A_l)$, and at least one of the inequalities holds as a strict inequality
- A_k and A_l are indifferent if $\Phi^+(A_k) = \Phi^+(A_l)$ and $\Phi^-(A_k) = \Phi^-(A_l)$
- A_k and A_l are incomparable otherwise.

In PROMETHEE I, some ordered pairs of alternatives are comparable; and some others are not.

5.4.5.2.5. The PROMETHEE II complete partial ranking

The net outranking flow allows a complete ranking of the alternatives and avoids any incomparability. The net outranking flow is defined as

$$\Phi(A_k) = \Phi^+(A_k) - \Phi^-(A_k)$$

The PROMETHEE II complete ranking is then define as

- A_k is preferred to A_l if $\Phi(A_k) > \Phi(A_l)$
- A_k and A_l are indifferent if $\Phi(A_k) = \Phi(A_l)$

The alternative with the highest $\Phi(A_k)$ can be considered the best one.

The six types of preference function and the partial or complete preorder in PROMETHEE I or II provide the decision maker more insights in solving the given problem.

PROMETHEE takes into account the amplitude of the deviations between the evaluations of the alternatives within each criterion, eliminates the scaling effects, reduces the number of incomparabilities, and provides information on the conflicting nature of the criteria.

PROMETHEE (as all outranking methods) can simultaneously deal with qualitative and quantitative criteria. Criteria scores can be expressed in their own units.

PROMETHEE requires too many thresholds to define the preference function. The threshold parameters are rather subjective. PROMETHEE suffers from rank reversal when a new alternative is introduced. PROMETHEE does not provide the possibility to structure a decision problem. In case of many alternatives and criteria, it becomes difficult for the decision maker to obtain a clear view of the problem and to evaluate the results. PROMETHEE does not provide a weighting method.

CONCLUSIONS

The existence of an energy efficiency gap and market barriers to energy efficiency investment has been known since the early 1970s. Barriers to energy efficiency can be defined as “postulated mechanisms that inhibit investment in technologies that are both energy efficient and economically efficient”.

Based on the theoretical efforts with which energy efficiency barriers are approached, we make a distinction between three major categories of barriers:

- Market failures;
- Behavioural failures;
- Modelling failures.

Within each of those categories, we identify the most relevant types of barriers, describe their main characteristics, and provide a comprehensive overview of empirical research.

The point of departure in all instances are the theories (e.g. Rational Choice Theory or Behavioural economics) that try to explain the existence of those barriers. The boundaries are not always all that clear, as behavioural economics might just as well be called “psychological economics”. Also, “information problems” can be found in all three main categories. In the case of “modelling failures”, the general idea is that there are in fact no barriers, and that market actors always act “rationally”.

There exists limited “hard” empirical evidence for all three categories. The empirical evidence is by no means consistently strong among or across those categories. In fact, even the body of economic research is not conclusive (and to some extent contradictory) on the fundamentals of energy efficiency economics.

Because behavioural economics have thus far avoided the fundamental question of how to reconcile revealed preference theory with the existence of behavioural failures, the last chapter provides a broad

overview of multicriteria decision aiding (MCDA) techniques, to find out whether preference elicitation with MCDA may potentially provide part of the answer.

Human behaviour in decision-making has a number of characteristics (Larichev, 1999).

- Decision-makers have a limited span of the short-term memory. This limitation manifests itself in eliminating some of the criteria, grouping the alternatives, and so on;
- Decision-makers are unable to take into account small differences in the evaluations. This limited exactness in quantitative measurements can lead to e.g. elimination of the dominating alternatives; or a slight difference in the criteria weights can change the order of the alternatives preference. Decision-makers can also poorly measure probabilities in a quantitative way;
- Decision-makers make errors when processing information, e.g. due to lack of attention, habitual heuristics, etc.;
- Decision-makers do not have preconceived decision rules in new decision problems, and usually fall back on a kind of “trial and error” approach;
- Decision-makers can only pay attention to a limited number of objects in every step of the decision-making process. They make a preliminary selection of the best alternatives and compare pairwise the selected alternatives, checking for dominance. The decision rules used when comparing can vary, as human preferences of the alternatives and criteria are very unstable;
- Decision-makers seek satisfactory decisions rather than optimal ones.

Multicriteria decision-making evolved from cost-benefit analysis (CBA), using mathematical models to support decision-making involving trade-offs. CBA takes a monetary unit as the common unit of measurement. In MCDA, attributes may characterize the social, economic, cultural or ecological significance of the alternatives.

The distinction between normative and positive aspects of decision-making in MCDA methods is ambiguous. Normative approaches derive rationality by postulating a priori norms as necessary for rational behaviour. Descriptive approaches derive rationality from observing how decision-makers make decisions in real life. Prescriptive approaches *discover* rationality models for a given decision-maker from his answers to preference-related questions. Constructive approaches *build* rationality models for a given decision-maker from his answers to preference-related questions (Dias and Tsoukias, 2003). A number of outranking MCDA methods (e.g. ELECTRE) explicitly refer to the constructive approach.

We are concerned with formal models of the decision-makers preferences. Modelling decision-making begins with a formal approach, a mathematical expression of the preference function. Utility theory, a normative decision method, is commonly used to describe preferences.

Utility and value based MCDA approaches (e.g. MAUT/MAVT, SMART) assume that the decision-maker has an internal utility or value function used to measure the “utility” of any outcome. The decision-maker’s preferences are modelled by utility / value functions (*intra*-criteria preferences) and criteria weights (*inter*-criteria comparisons). In normative utility theory, rational economic decision-makers are assumed to follow certain postulates. For example, decision-maker always prefer more to less, but sometimes at least at a diminishing rate on a continuous scale of value. Pareto optimality is inferred from always preferring more than less of a commodity. The axioms also assert that a decision-maker can compare all alternatives and that he is transitive. MAVT complements the axioms of connectivity and transitivity by the axioms (condition) of independence. Preference independence states that the comparisons of alternatives in two criteria are valid if their estimates in other criteria are fixed at any level (Larichev, 1999, p. 5). Studies about systematic and predicted economic intransitivity have identified limitations with the rational economic models. These studies were among the first to demonstrate a gap between the requirements of decision methods (normative aspects) and the possibilities of the human information processing system (descriptive aspects).

Decision-making involves high levels of uncertainty. A key factor in defining a utility function is the risk attitude of the decision-maker. MAUT and ELECTRE belong to the quantitative risk category of MCDA approaches. A representation of preferences where certainty is assured is called a value function. MAVT methods belong to the quantitative riskless category of MCDA approaches. AHP uses the same

paradigm as MAVT. Quantitative methods like MAUT/MAVT require the data to be measured in cardinal or ratio terms. Cardinal utility relies on the assumptions of irreducibility of needs and perfect knowledge. In reality, decision-makers are aware that the cost of gathering complete information may be too high and hence settle for the best information they can get. Without complete knowledge it is not possible to optimize. Decision-makers often “satisfice” or rely on “heuristics”. MCDA approaches such as some non-compensatory methods (e.g. the dominance method) that screen or filter discrete sets of alternatives involve standards of attainment that may not be optimal.

Human preferences are difficult to measure objectively. Mathematical models express the fundamental nature of the decision-making problem. It is often tempting to leave out those parts of reality that are difficult to measure accurately, wrongly assuming that they are not critically important. The ideal of MAUT methods for instance is total objectivity. Trade-offs are expressed in abstract terms combined with utility scales ideally based on objective measures. Time limitations, complexities of the decision problem and measurement difficulties make it difficult to obtain objectivity. A decision support system should provide means to include information that can only be expressed subjectively. It is possible in principle to use subjective scales in MAUT/MAVT methods. AHP quantifies the subjective using a verbal subjective scale of measure for both the criteria values and the relative criteria weights. Methods like AHP are based on qualitative data but use a shift to quantitative variables (i.e. an equivalent quantitative assessment of qualitative data).

In many decision problems the estimates of the main variables (criteria) are in a verbal form, usually located on the ordinal scales of the criteria. Qualitative MCDA methods use only ordinal preferences. Methods based on the disaggregation (or ordinal regression) paradigm like UTA use an indirect approach of preference elicitation, e.g. in an ordinal form of ranking the alternatives. Methods based on the Verbal Decision Analysis (VDA) paradigm are oriented on only using ordinal judgments in preference elicitation. There is no shift to quantitative variables. Ordinal methods are often used because they require less cognitive effort and a lower degree of abstract reasoning from the decision-maker. They also reduce measurement errors made by decision-makers. Mixed quantitative and qualitative methods apply different decision rules based on the type of data (Herath and Prato, 2006, p. 5).

It is unnatural for decision-makers to state their preferences in mathematical form. Interactions between criteria make the construction of utility or value functions even more challenging. Preferences, even revealed preferences, are hard to identify. If no preference information is available, seeking the minimum distance to an ideal point is often used (e.g. TOPSIS). But there are no reasons to expect that a decision-maker’s preference point in that direction (Olson, 2000, p. 14).

Brauers and Ginevicius (2009) identify six (6) conditions that a “most robust” MCDA method has to satisfy:

- MCDA has to take into consideration “Consumer Sovereignty”. Consumer sovereignty is the power of consumers to determine what commodities are produced, and suggests that consumers rather than producers are the best judge of what product benefit them the most;
- MCDA has to consider all non-correlated criteria rather than a limited number of criteria;
- MCDA has to consider all interactions between criteria and alternatives *at the same time*, rather than examining these interactions two by two;
- MCDA has to be non-subjective rather than use subjective estimations;
- MCDA has to be based on cardinal numbers rather than ordinal numbers;
- MCDA has to use the most recent data.

Empirical evidence suggests that MCDA methods are not readily accepted by decision-makers. They tend to prefer relatively simple, easy to understand techniques, which they perceive to be more accurate. The preference elicitation technique (absolute measurement, pairwise comparisons, ordinal judgments, rankings, ...) used within an MCDA method influence the decision-maker’s willingness to accept that MCDA method. For example, compensatory strategies (e.g. pair-wise comparisons between alternatives on some criterion) where the decision-maker has to make explicit trade-off between alternatives may cause “decisional conflict”. Decisional conflict is defined as the negative affective state induced by making trade-off judgments.

A decisions support system will also have to take into account that preferences of decision-makers will vary according to value systems influenced by culture.

Research has not consistently shown that any MCDA method is objectively superior to all other methods ([Aloysius et al, 2003, p. 5](#)).

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